

D3.1 Framework Development

Introducing the Risk-Tandem Framework

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Executive summary

This deliverable provides a state-of-the-art review of existing governance methods used within the context of Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and serves as a proof of concept for the implementation of the Risk-Tandem Framework. It further outlines progress made so far with the governance analysis, needs assessments, and other conceptual development and engagement processes with the Real-World Labs (RWLs).

Developing and applying the Risk-Tandem Framework is a central part of the DIRECTED Project's goals, providing a participatory, co-productive, and integrative approach towards multi-hazard risks throughout the RWLs and beyond the scope of the Project. Specifically, the RWLs can be seen a testing grounds and springboard to demonstrate the value of the Risk-Tandem Framework, as well as refine it for its application in other settings and locations.

The report is structured in the following way. The introductory section provides a brief outline of the Risk-Tandem Framework and its underlying methodology, describing its application to risk governance within the DIRECTED Project, and recaps existing approaches and challenges faced so far within the risk governance community.

In the following section, we delve into the various risk governance frameworks implemented in DIRECTED for the integrated shaping of the Risk-Tandem Framework, to further demonstrate how the framework is applied to the context of the RWLs. Aligning with Task 3.1 in the Grant Agreement, our focus is on integrating advanced governance methods to enhance knowledge, foster co-creative user and stakeholder engagement, and ensure accountability. The Frameworks employed include the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) framework, as an overarching conceptual landscape; the International Risk Governance Council's (IRGC) Risk Governance Framework on risk governance in general; the SHIELD model ("Sharing Knowledge, Harmonising Capacities, Institutionalizing Coordination, Engaging Stakeholders, Leveraging Investments, Developing Communications"), aimed at synergizing DRM and CCA strategies; the Risk Layering Approach, quantifying and assessing the economic aspects of risk governance; and the Tandem Framework, guiding co-creation and co-production processes. These frameworks are presented, and their various strengths and limitations are highlighted.

In section three, the Risk-Tandem Framework is introduced as a tool to enhance communication and cooperation across institutions, sectors and scales of all actors involved in DRM and CCA. Combining and further enhancing the existing approaches through one unified framework further addresses the second part of the Grant Agreement's Task 3.1, namely "merging the International Risk Governance Council's Risk Governance Framework with the Tandem Framework developed by SEI, the Risk Layering approach put forth by IIASA, and scoping alignment with other governance frameworks for DRR and CCA planning and decision-making processes, such as the SHIELD model from the ESPRESSO Project."

The conclusion and application section finally proposes first steps towards the practical application of the Risk-Tandem Framework to the various RWLs and the risk governance challenges they face.

The main aim of this deliverable is to present the newly developed Risk-Tandem Framework. This is done by describing how state-of-the-art governance approaches have been synthesized with co-creative stakeholder engagement processes, and presenting the critical learnings from the research of value to practitioners, policy, and user communities in general. The deliverable features a methodology section, alongside a schematic description of how the framework will be applied throughout the remainder of the project. This deliverable is targeted towards a general audience interested in DRM and CCA approaches. However, scholars and general readers more focused on the conceptual and theoretical underpinnings supporting the development process of the Risk-Tandem Framework will find a deep dive into the various approaches synthesized throughout in Section 1 and 2. Practitioners and those most interested in its application, will find detailed information on the practical and co-creative relationship between Risk-Tandem Framework and the RWLs in section 3.

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List of abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
ESPREsso	Enhancing Synergies for Disaster Prevention in the European Union
IRGC	International Risk Governance Council
RWL	Real-World Lab
RTF	Risk-Tandem Framework
WP	Work Package
IAD	Institutional Analysis & Development

1 Introduction

Moving towards a disaster-resilient society, the DIRECTED Project aims to overcome silos, develop capacities and sustainable cooperation, strengthen multi-risk thinking, utilise synergies, and promote the concept of interoperability. In this context the Risk-Tandem Framework (RTF) supports Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) planning and decision-making processes and seeks to build long-term governance capacity for information and knowledge integration and interoperability.

As defined by UNDRR (UN, 2017), DRM is “the application of Disaster Risk Reduction policies and strategies to prevent new disaster risk, reduce existing disaster risk and manage residual risk, contributing to the strengthening of resilience and reduction of disaster losses.” The global Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 – 2030 guides the development of national DRM strategies or plans outlining goals, objectives and associated actions (measures) for reducing disaster risks. As such, Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) is the policy objective of DRM. The implementation of DRM and associated measures is often connected to a cycle which evolves through phases of prevention, encompassing mitigation (e.g., managed retreat, risk zoning, dikes/ levees), preparedness (e.g., early warning and forecasting systems, temporary flood barriers), response (e.g., evacuation centers, pumping equipment) and recovery (e.g., insurance, reconstruction). European level regulations target specific natural hazards, like the Floods Directive (2007/60/EC), guiding the assessment and management of flood risk across EU Member States supporting the implementation of prevention and risk reduction strategies. The EU Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre (DRMKC) supports Member States in translating complex scientific data and analysis into advice and information to guide their DRM policies. Civil protection or emergency management policies and relevant plans from national to local levels, support disaster preparedness and response, and subsequent residual risk management. The EU Civil Protection Mechanism strengthens cooperation between EU members and participating states civil protection agencies to improve prevention, preparedness, and response to disasters and requires the development of National Risk Assessments.

More frequent and extreme weather events like heatwaves, floods and droughts, are expected due to increasing greenhouse gas emissions, resulting in global temperature increases and rising sea levels. Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) supports taking action to prepare for, and adjust to, both the current effects of climate change as well as predicted future impacts. The legally binding international treaty on climate change is the Paris Agreement 2015 aiming to limit temperature increase to 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goal 13 addresses climate action. At the European level, the European Commission’s EU Adaptation Strategy (2021) outlines how the EU can adapt to the unavoidable impacts of climate change and become climate resilient by 2050. In response to global and EU level policies, Member States have developed tailored laws and frameworks for enabling climate mitigation and adaptation nationally. Climate risk assessments, National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), regional/local adaptation plans and sectoral adaptation plans are being developed by EU countries (see progress up to 2021 in EEA Report 2020). Examples of such adaptation measures include nature-based coastal protection to adapt to increased frequency and intensity of coastal storms, adapted farming practices to deal with longer periods of drought and hospital cooling measures to adapt to extreme heat. EU initiatives like the European Climate Risk Assessment, EU Mission on Adaptation and Climate-ADAPT Platform, aim to accelerate the implementation of such plans by facilitating knowledge exchange, guidance, and financing targeting regional and local authorities.

Although DRM and CCA have emerged in different policy arenas, associated frameworks and policies do recognize the need for integration, alignment and coherence to capture efficiencies and synergies. However, gaps in governance, capacity, communication and data/modelling are hindering efforts to achieve integration between national to local levels (Islam et al. 2020). DRM and CCA clearly have common goals to manage and adapt to climate-related hazards, but the responsible agencies and institutional structures typically differ, making it difficult to align their risk assessment and management processes. Therefore, there is a growing need to facilitate collaboration and exchange across these domains to align the national, regional and local knowledge, capacities, policies and interventions to capture synergies across DRM and CCA activities, and efficiently manage limited financial resources.

The DIRECTED project aims to facilitate integration between DRM and CCA activities and support collaboration between all actors engaged across institutions, sectors and geographic scales. We approach this challenge through the lens of interoperability aiming to improve the connectivity of data, models, and tools, as well as the exchange of information and improved communication and availability of governance mechanisms to support more integrated DRM and CCA knowledge, policies and interventions. Figure 1 presents the overall framing of integrating DRM and CCA through enabling governance, data and model, and information interoperability. For example, governance interoperability could be facilitated through established partnerships that enable exchange and co-benefits across CCA and emergency planning with agencies operating through different administrative and geographical boundaries. An example of information interoperability would be to enable municipal and civil protection agencies to collectively communicate their needs to inform risk assessments that use the latest climate projections and have the appropriate level of granularity to guide practices such as planning evaluation routes or allocating temporary flood barriers. An example of data and model interoperability would be facilitating (open) data standards, (meta) data management processes, and communication of uncertainty and modelling bias to encourage connectivity between municipal and/or civil protection data and modelling systems enabling increased interoperable climate and disaster risk assessments, across organizations within the same catchment or coastal zone area.

The RTF aims to support DRM and CCA actors to understand the risk governance context, co-produce risk knowledge to inform policy and management practices, and strengthen coordination and collaboration to sustain integrated approaches and actions.

Through the RWLs, DIRECTED is facilitating transdisciplinary exchange and learning between natural and social science experts, relevant public actors, and private/ civil society stakeholders to address the complexity of risk and support integrating DRM and CCA into policy and practice. Through the design, implementation, and refinement of the RTF in the RWLs, it will be contextualized to the needs of local and regional DRM and CCA actors. Risk-Tandem will support actors to address governance challenges and enhance interoperability of decision-making, regulatory, and procedural processes. The RTF will act as an enabler, facilitating data and model interoperability using interconnected models and a flexible Data Fabric for DRM/CCA decision-making and information interoperability by supporting the flow of information between phases and actors working across DRM/CCA. Importantly, the learnings from the RWLs will help evolve the RTF towards becoming a generalizable approach. This ensures that the framework will be applicable in other (European) regions beyond the DIRECTED project's lifespan.

Figure 1: Integrating DRM & CCA by enabling interoperability in the DIRECTED project.

1.1 Methodology

The aim of Work Package 3 is to provide an innovative and empirically tested risk governance framework.¹ The objective set out in Task 3.1 in the DIRECTED Grant Agreement accordingly states that WP 3 will: “Develop[e] an innovative and integrated risk governance framework for DRR and CCA (Risk-Tandem Framework)” (Grant Agreement No. 101073978, page 10). Specifically, this deliverable fulfills the Task 3.1 Framework development: “This task aims to integrate current state-of-the-art governance approaches towards user and stakeholder engagement and increased accountability. This involves merging the International Risk Governance Council’s Risk Governance Framework with the Tandem framework developed by SEI, the Risk Layering approach put forth by IIASA, and scoping alignment with other governance frameworks for DRR and CCA planning and decision-making processes, such as the SHIELD model from the ESPREsSO project.” This deliverable is a foundational piece based on theoretical scholarship and applied practice, combining existing risk governance, knowledge co-production, risk management, and participatory approaches into one holistic framework.

The framework’s combination of top-down theoretical scholarship integrated with a bottom-up co-production approach towards learning and shared solutions has important methodological implications. This combined approach is a central innovation of the DIRECTED project, and a unique characteristic of the RTF, setting it apart from existing Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation approaches. Importantly, the tools

¹When referring to governance, we follow the three different but overlapping aspects of the term, namely governance as structure, as process, and as mechanism (Levi-Faur 2012, p. 8).

developed as part of the RTF will be primarily applied by the RWL hosts themselves, which in turn feeds off the continuing capacity development and training for trainers' strategy (see also the Capacity Development, Deliverable 1.2). However, it is helpful to spell out the underlying methodology that guides the conceptualization, application, and iteration of the RTF.

Like any other conceptual framework, the RTF relies on a set of theoretical, ontological, and normative assumptions that inevitably propel its application in the respective RWLs into certain directions and away from others. This means, **DIRECTED in general and the Risk-Tandem in particular are neither theoretically nor normatively neutral**. This theoretical background also shapes the kinds of questions asked throughout the project's lifecycle, and more specifically the criteria used to measure and evaluate the RWLs. Consequently, the following baseline claims and assumptions are made when investigating the various RWLs.

1. Broad and meaningful stakeholder participation throughout the decision-making process on Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaption matters. This assumption is based on Task 3.1's call for knowledge co-production to support continuous user and stakeholder engagement and increased accountability. WP 3 achieves this through the use of the Tandem framework, as well as the SHIELD Model, and the IRGC framework.
2. The DIRECTED project is guided by the assumption that regional stakeholders understand their problems best, and might already have solutions at hand. At the same time, the RWLs may require guidance and support to collaboratively identify gaps and opportunities to strengthen existing systems to facilitate innovation. Consequently, the precise needs and requirements for improvement of each RWL also depend on their specific context. The RTF does not offer an exhaustive list of indicators, but rather presents central pillars of DRM and CCA, such as participation, communication, and knowledge co-production for example that can then be used to develop indicators tailored to the requirements of the RWLs.
3. The RTF is conceptually and practically context-sensitive, adding to its generic applicability. This also allows the framework to produce insights and recommendations in RWLs where more structural changes are difficult due to rigid policy circumstances.
4. The RTF is dynamic in nature, inviting and necessitating contextual iteration and refinement based on the varying needs and wants of the respective regions. This dynamism affects the way in which research results, insights, and assessments can be reported.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, Task 3.1 (to which this report refers) entails the development of the RTF. Thus, within months 1 – 16, conceptual and scholarly work has been carried out in a communal effort by the RIFS, SEI, UCC, and the IIASA to synthesize a broad range of state-of-the-art DRM and CCA frameworks into one coherent approach. Various workshops, serious games, and scoping consultations with the RWL leaders have been held in order to account for the co-creative demands of the RTF, and a schematic tool for the institutional stakeholder assessment has been developed (for a detailed listing of the work done so far, see Annexes I – V).

While the general methodology of the RTF is wide-ranging, given its holistic nature, a few cornerstones of the governance and knowledge co-production approach can be highlighted via the example of a General Assembly, on-site visit, and serious game workshop meeting held in September 2023 in Cologne, Germany.

For example, the Rhine-Erft's regional waterboard, the Erftverband, presented an overview of their work and authority, accompanied by a field trip to the local dams and water management sites. From a governance perspective, the relevant partners gained insights into how communication among the various stakeholders works, and what the central struggles of the Erftverband are with regards to flood protection. A workshop and serious game "Breaking Silos" hosted by SEI and supported by RIFS sought to demonstrate the complexity of governing risks in multi-hazard contexts, highlighting the need for clear communication channels, especially with regards to how different societal actors can be involved in DRM and CCA decision-making and who needs what kind of information to participate in the process.

In summary, the RTF serves as a conceptual and practical guideline towards the existing governance approaches in the RWLs. At the same time, the RTF is not a rigid framework that works with an X number of immutable indicators which would neatly represent a static interpretation of reality. Rather, its dynamic nature necessitates re-iteration and development,

based on the context in which it is applied. Thus, its heuristic benefits and innovative character, allow for evolution and progressive improvement.

1.2 Risk governance and the Risk-Tandem Framework

DIRECTED Task 3.1 ‘Framework development’ integrates current state-of-the-art governance approaches for improved knowledge integration by means of co-production approaches towards user and stakeholder engagement and increased accountability.

This involves merging the International Risk Governance Council’s (IRGC) Risk Governance Framework with the Tandem Framework developed by SEI, the Risk Layering approach put forth by IIASA, and scoping alignment with other governance frameworks for DRR and CCA planning and decision-making processes, such as the SHIELD Model from the ESPRESSO Project.²

The RTF’s core concepts and methodologies are explored, clarified, and brought to generic use for further research in the field through the application of the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) Framework (Polski & Ostrom, 2017).

Present Deliverable D3.1, the initial version of the RTF, will be revised based on the application and evaluation in the RWLs.

1.3 Understanding risk

Understanding the complex and systemic nature of climate and disaster risks is crucial for countries to effectively implement global policies including the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030, the Paris Agreement, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The assessment, measurement, modelling and governance of risks is multi-layered and necessitates an interdisciplinary approach due to very different types of interactions and processes that can happen, e.g., between and across economic, socio-political, physical, or other dimensions. Recently a detailed review on such approaches was performed by Gill et al. (2022), which distinguished between different types of hazard events and dynamics, as well as combinations of different hazards. Starting from the traditional representation of disaster risk and impacts as a function of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability (IPCC 2012), they included dynamic risks through the inclusion of time components in each of these elements as well as possible interactions over time. In this context, the framework for complex climate change risk assessment from Simpson et al. (2021) was discussed in detail as it provides a way forward from single to multi-risk analysis of natural hazard events.

Essentially, complexity increases from the first level which focuses on single drivers for each determinant of risk, to the second level where multiple drivers interact with determinants of risks, to the third level with interacting risks as shown in Figure 2 below.

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/700342>

Figure 2: Three categories of increasing complex risk. Source: Simpson et al. (2021).

Similar to the conceptualisation above, interactions and interdependencies are a major dimension now in the analysis of risks due to natural hazard events across many scales and dimensions, including single to multi-hazard analysis as well as single-, to multi- and systemic risk analysis (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2022). However, despite calls for the application of multi-risk assessment and management approaches, there are challenges in their implementation, particularly in real-world settings. Schlumberger et al. (2022) undertook a detailed review of current practices, policies and policy-making processes on global and regional levels, with a specific focus on the EU. They conclude that such approaches need further consideration, especially in sectoral policies, and the scientific community needs to embed the considerations of good governance principles into the development and testing of proposed new tools. In this context, avoiding miscommunication and confusion by providing a joint terminology for such assessment is considered essential (Duncan et al. 2021). One additional main challenge identified is around the strategic application of co-production approaches and methods, in efforts to support and complement the implementation of (often) expert-led and – developed frameworks that may otherwise fail in producing contextually appropriate and relevant information. These will be explored further in the following chapters, leading to the establishment of the conceptual RTF.

1.4 On the issue of complex and systemic risks

The Anthropocene presents an increasing number of risk-related challenges for the actors navigating the interface of science, policy, and practice, especially in the dimensions of prediction and risk management (DellaSala et al., 2018). Indeed, and in association with the progress of globalisation, new and more complex constellations of risks are emerging (Goldin & Mariathan, 2015). On the one hand, the growth of shared digital and physical infrastructures as well as interconnected supply chains continue to generate vulnerabilities in the world system, making it susceptible to cascading ripple effects of disturbances (UNDRR, 2022; Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023). The triple disaster of Fukushima Daichi in 2011 and the eruption of the Eyjafjallajökull Volcano in 2010 (Bravo-Laguna, 2020) can both serve as extreme examples of global and transboundary disasters with a geographically limited origin. Flooding also tends to connect nations sharing river basins, while droughts can encompass entire continents. Consequently, risk managers must begin thinking beyond nations and isolated systems toward understanding the networked complexity of disaster risks, and how hazards elsewhere may lead to local disruptions following the cascade of events through shared dependencies (UNDRR, 2022; Pescaroli, et al., 2018).

On the other hand, socio-economic vulnerabilities and the pressures imposed by climate change are also on the rise. Persisting economic stratification, poverty, inequality, conflict, and

marginalisation continue exacerbating and creating disaster risks, especially in settings that discourage social protection and emphasize personal responsibility over risk management (Bankoff and Hilhorst, 2022). It is also important to note that historical injustices and chronic structural conditions advanced by certain modes of development underpinning these issues are often neglected in risk management interventions, and thus the root causes behind vulnerabilities tend to remain unaddressed (IPCC 2023; UNDRR, 2022; Wisner, 2020; Oliver-Smith and Hoffman, 2020; Sillmann, 2022). Yet, as illustrated by the COVID-19 pandemic, these underlying pressures are ever-present, and once triggered, may have crippling outcomes for those vulnerable and marginalised following disruptions to safety, health, employment, mobility, communication, and finance (Ringsmuth, et al., 2022). In the case of COVID-19 alone, numerous countries witnessed a widespread reversal of development gains in various dimensions and 97 million people were forced into poverty across the globe, especially in the Global South (UNDRR, 2022). Thus, one could suggest that global systems, supply chains and infrastructures are wholly unprepared for systemic disturbances that require collective management and overarching vulnerability reduction – a concern that extends to climate change and other risks such as biodiversity loss as well (Ringsmuth, et al., 2022; Sillmann, 2022).

Bearing similar systemic and destabilising global socio-economic effects of COVID-19, climate change has an aggravating effect on hydrometeorological hazards and vulnerabilities. Firstly, it erodes the stability of socio-ecological systems in terms of their capacity to support biodiversity and human activities, including the ability to cultivate land (Kelman, et al., 2015). Secondly, it continues to reshape the pathways leading to socio-economic vulnerabilities and creates other concerns for development, such as the ongoing loss of stable water supplies and safe land (ibid). These may have further and undetermined effects ranging from increased human mobility and displacement to conflicts triggered by scarcity, which in turn also may magnify vulnerabilities, further reducing the capacity for adaptation, in decades to come. In short, climate change reinforces existing systemic risks, leads to new systemic vulnerabilities, and challenges traditional reactive remedial measures.

A need for holistic risk governance has thus emerged. As put forward in the 2022 Global Assessment Report on Disaster Risk Reduction, such hyperconnected globality requires cultivating an understanding of its complexity beyond single hazards, localised incidents, and closed systems (UNDRR, 2022). Instead, it is necessary to advance the notion of systemic risk, with a focus on bridging connections between complex socio-ecological systems (including socio-economic vulnerabilities and governance systems) natural hazards and climate change, in efforts to begin categorising and addressing risks in novel ways (Renn et al., 2022; Sillmann et al., 2022). In this regard, one of the key concerns is to focus on understanding how risks and their cascading effects transgress scales, sectors, and spatial boundaries within and across other systems and regions (Schweizer, 2021; Schweizer and Renn, 2019), with a reference to the underpinning socio-political and economic issues that shape them (Sillmann, et al, 2019).

Uncertainty and ambiguity are also central features of systemic and complex risks (Renn, 2008; Berkes, 2017; Sillmann, et al., 2022). Given the complexity of interdependencies, feedback loops and near-endless number of potential connections that exist within ‘a system’ – depending on where its conceptual boundaries have been set – unknown factors are bound to influence all systemic risk estimations. In terms of ambiguity, referring to the ‘plurality of legitimate viewpoints’ (Renn, et al., 2011:233), the study of complexity often involves numerous disciplines and professionals sharing diverging perceptions regarding issues at hand. As a result, conceptualisations of complex systems and systemic risks usually mirror the priorities (or respective and preferred biases) of disciplines involved in defining them.

Ambiguity, complexity, and uncertainty also affect the ethical evaluation of the systemic risks, raising the question of how relevant or important these risks are. Uncertain empirical situations can lead to a genuine form of ‘normative uncertainty’ (Taebi et al. 2020; Hofbauer 2023), i.e., situations where stakeholders might not know what the right (just or fair) course of action is, since it is unclear what kind of values will be affected. For this reason, it is necessary to also look at the ethical justifiability of imposing risks, rather than focusing merely on the potential outcomes which are shrouded in uncertainty and ambiguity. Ambiguity has been used in a similar vein. However, the concept of ambiguity often entails that empirical information is available, but its applicability and the conclusions we draw from those facts can be reasonably debated. This contrasts the notion with uncertainty, wherein the information itself is often up for interpretation.

Further building upon the issue of biases and perception, it is also useful to interrogate the processes of what Kelman and Lewis (2012) describe as ‘disaster risk creation’, referring to the beliefs, values and acts of governance which contribute to ecological degradation, inequalities, and marginalisation of some. After all, socio-ecological systems are not neutral nor simply exist in the world, for they are of social origin (Walker and Cooper, 2011), despite their common representation through naturalistic metaphors (MacKinnon and Derickson, 2012). As such, their components, and relationships within are shaped by ideologies and relations of power.³ Which, if assumed neutral by systems discourse, naturalise ‘a system’ in a manner that absorbs all potential for achieving change (Walker and Cooper, 2011; MacKinnon and Derickson, 2012). Climate sciences and acts of governance that may disregard the ontological consequences of certain epistemologies when placing climate as their object of study are an example of such processes. Indeed, the depoliticised naturalisation of a system that equally reproduces the issue whilst generating seemingly objective solutions for its management constitutes a discursive and expertly policed boundary to innovation and change (Schulz and Siriwardane, 2015).⁴ Consequently, it is often not enough to measure and map a system. Instead, one must also seek transformations, novel approaches, and non-systemic solutions, if assumed that the system itself is a part of the problem formulation (Schulz and Siriwardane, 2015; Walker and Cooper, 2011).

Arguments as presented above create numerous challenges for those involved in managing systemic risks. These challenges include the need to reflect on the systemic dependencies that potentially unjust historical power structures have created, and accounting for the ambiguity as well as uncertainty involved in analysing systemic risks.

Going beyond managerial, uniform, and simplified solutions, one must increasingly consider the systemic and complex nature of risks, including their correlating, cascading and transboundary tendencies in technological and social dimensions (Renn et al., 2022; Sillmann, et al., 2022). There is also a need to strive toward holistic approaches in terms of accommodating not only current risks, which remain multifaceted insofar as they are approached beyond hazards, from the perspective of the vulnerability paradigm (Bankoff and Hilhorst, 2022), but also by assuming a future-oriented perspective with regards to projected effects of climate change. This necessitates the commitment to collaboration and transdisciplinary engagement across the fields of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, Climate Change Adaptation, and associated sub-disciplines and practices. Finally, one must accommodate considerations for uncertainty and ambiguity as well (Sillmann, et al., 2022; Berkes, 2017; Renn, et al., 2011). These topics thus premise the case for adaptive governance (Berkes, 2017) fit to address systemic risks and cope with uncertainties through transdisciplinary and cross-sectoral cooperation across scales (Sillmann, et al., 2022).

In essence, in today’s interconnected world, risks and disasters are complex and connected globally through technology, the environment, and society. For example, a disaster in one country or region can affect supply chains and economies worldwide. Additionally, climate change and social inequalities are making these risks even more challenging. Therefore, we need a comprehensive and collaborative approach to understand and manage these risks, considering not just the direct immediate dangers but also the underlying social and economic factors and indirect effects of disasters. This approach is essential for effectively dealing with the complicated and interconnected challenges of our modern world.

³ Often in association with neoliberalism, in particular.

⁴ A process that Deleuze would call ‘folding’, and what Foucault would describe as the processes of subjectification via the operations of discourse and power that simultaneously reproduce the condition of reality and its subjects through the voluntary reproduction of hegemonic knowledge and practices. One could also borrow from Baudrillard and the concept of simulacra to explore the issues of representing reality through its abstractions that inevitably escape reality itself over the lifetime of a simulation in decision making.

2 Risk governance: Schools of thought

The concept of ‘risk governance’ evolved over time. As it was influenced by political and economic theories (Klinke and Renn, 2019), there was a marked shift in governance from state-centric towards market-oriented, following the displacement of Keynesian economics by the ongoing neoliberalisation of the public and private spheres since the 1980s (Jessop, 2002; Comaroff and Comaroff, 2009; Rhodes, 2007; Braun, 2014). As a result, governance has mutated into an ‘ad hoc assemblage that in advanced capitalism proceeds in a relatively aimless fashion, introducing “management” [...] in a piecemeal and contingent way in response to a dynamic and changing world’ (Braun, 2014:51). More importantly, the absence of central states and the *longue durée* of capital has also led to the deployment of various free market-oriented legalities, policies, and ideologies shaping the social, geographical, political, and moral spheres to reconstruct a universe estranged from realities beyond the needs of the economy (Comaroff and Comaroff, 2009). Hence, when risk governance theorists claim the increasing risks of the 21st century alone have necessitated the reshaping of risk governance toward multi-scalar engagement (for example, Djalante and Lassa, 2019), it is helpful to keep in mind that this has occurred during a period of societal development disenfranchising centralised controls within large parts of the Global North. Moreover, to contest reductionism associated with Cartesian dualism, the generation of new risks is inherent to the progress of modernity (instead of something that can be associated to ‘nature’), thus constituting a paradox for their management (Beck, 1992).

Two challenges concerning implementing **multiscale and polycentric governance** should be noted. Firstly, following the fracturing, in some cases, of hierarchical governance into multiscale-networks and loose assemblages – a condition which Jessop (1998:8) described as the ‘heterarchy’ of autopoietic actors – has produced a landscape in which the applicability of once-popular *Steuerungstheorie*⁵ to practice is limited in the absence of actors capable of steering. Put simply, it is arduous to establish shared priorities and objectives for policy and polity when public management relies on the self-organisation of relatively autonomous parts engaged in a constant process of negotiation to establish a resemblance of order (Jessop, 1998). Consequently, when theorists discuss the need to effectively steer and govern⁶, one must acknowledge that such processes take place against polycentric and poly-contextual backdrops characterised by the divergence of values, beliefs, and ideologies (Luhmann, 1997; Bevir and Rhodes, 2006). Secondly, risk governance is negotiated with multiple discourses often not shared by different disciplines and practices: the fields of DRR and CCA, for example⁷, are often isolated and siloed from each other in terms of terminologies, approaches and financing despite having similar goals (Mercer, 2010; IRFC 2020, Chapter 6).

However, this is not to say that risk governance would be consumed by a status quo of administrative (nor discursive) chaos. For instance, some evidence from case studies in Europe and North America suggest that **polycentric governance can be beneficial**, with multiple levels of actors and governance supporting higher environmental benefits compared to monocentric governance (Newig and Fritsch, 2009). Furthermore, as the German governance tradition reminds us, hierarchical controls and self-regulating systems are not always mutually exclusive, since actors within usually progress toward solutions by producing dialogic combinations of the rules and ordering principles available to them (Mayntz, 1998). Instead, the purpose of aligning with the anti-essentialist trend above is to point out that the polycentricity and poly-contextuality of governance systems remain intertwined with certain ordering principles. For example, despite the validity of the claim describing the European Union as a supra-nationalist network of networks (Leonard, 1999), its member states and organisations remain bound by its regulatory capacities and legal mechanisms (Shore, 2006).⁸

⁵ As discussed by Mayntz (2006).

⁶ Applicable to risk governance and management, mentioned by Renn and Klinke (2019) as well.

⁷ Both can be in the sphere of risk governance.

⁸ Anecdotally exemplified by a policy relic that once sought to prevent the European consumers’ access to cucumbers below the ideal length of 30cm with a curvature of some 10mm for every 10cm as per the regulation No. 1677 of 1988.

Among such principles, the underpinning values and ideologies should be of researchers' primary interest as well. As critical theorists have pointed out (the hyper-bureaucratic theorising regarding the ontology of 'a governance'), there usually exists a tacit commitment to free markets which continue to enforce the surrender of hierarchical powers over fiscal control (Davies, 2012), among others.

Therefore, when Klinke and Renn (2019:2) continue to define risk governance as the marking of 'institutional structures and socio-political processes that guide and restrain collective activities of a group, society, or international community to influence or direct the course of *events or people's behaviour when dealing with risk issues*', it is good to bear in mind that these structures and processes remain characterised by rules and hierarchies of power since the influence over politics and policies is unequally distributed across governance actors.⁹ More importantly, it is necessary to spell out what can, in theory, be implicitly embedded 'socio-political processes' as described by Klinke and Renn; that politico-economically non-neutral and sometimes damaging policies, behaviours and ideologies shape not only risks but also limit the pathways which risk management may leverage (Lewis and Kelman, 2012). These arguments may also become useful in contesting the depoliticization and naturalisation of unnatural and inherently political systems in complex systems though, as discussed in the previous chapter. The concept of 'interactive' or social-political governance considers interaction as a mutually influencing relation between two or more entities including civil, private and public actors (Kooiman, 1999; Kooiman et al. 2008). Institutionalisation emphasises the interconnected process of patterns arising in people's actions, and how fluid behaviour gradually solidifies into structures, and those structures in turn structure behaviour (Arts et al. 2006), connecting with the idea of 'structure-agency interplay' (Giddens 1984; Kooiman 2016). To enable such interactive governance in practice, Sørensen (2013) argues that it can be meta governed through 'soft' reflexive law and institutional features to guide networks and partnerships if they cannot be institutionalised through 'hard' rules and regulations. With these in mind, one can now venture further into the practicalities of systemic risk management, and why these should be complimented via the methods of co-production.

In summary, risk governance has evolved from state-centric to market-oriented systems, creating a more complex and varied approach to managing risks. This has resulted in siloed fields like Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation, which all have a shared goal but vary in their focus and thus theoretical assumptions and output. Polycentric governance, though complex, can be effective, especially when informed by flexible, 'soft' norms and inclusive, co-productive approaches. Understanding this dynamic is crucial for managing the multifaceted nature of modern risks.

2.1 Governing systemic risk: Approaches, frameworks, and methods

The complexities of modern risk landscapes as discussed above, has led to the emergence of holistic risk governance. Indeed, there is a need to strive towards adaptive and transformative governance that can, on one hand, manage systemic issues through knowledge integration, and on the other, cope with uncertainty (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023; Sillmann, et al., 2022; Berkes, 2017; Renn and Schweizer, 2009). Yet, it remains undecided how to translate these aspirations into policy options and action (Deubelli and Mechler, 2021). To bridge these gaps, we introduce some frameworks, methods, and approaches for complexity management, coping with uncertainty and ambiguity associated with systemic risks. While not the focus of this report, it is important to note that several modelling tools developed throughout the DIRECTED Project in the respective RWLs also

⁹ To refine – without contesting – their later argument that 'no single actor in our societies possess the knowledge, capabilities, or resources to steer and manage complex risks that originate in complexity-rich ecological, social, and economic systems' (Klinke and Renn, 2019:2).

play a role in assessing, mapping, and supporting decision-making (see outputs by WP 2 and 5, particularly D5.1).

2.1.1 The institutional context of risk governance

A conceptual landscape through institutional analysis and development

Before exploring the various frameworks that inform and help construct the RTF, it is important to clarify the conceptual and ontological assumptions this work is based on. As an overarching conceptual landscape, the RTF builds on the Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) Framework developed by Elinor Ostrom (Ostrom 2010). As such, the IAD serves as a heuristic approach to understand what the relevant institutions of the RWLs consist of, how they function, and how they act under a given set of circumstances.

The IAD provides a framework to analyse the institutional structures that govern each system, the actors that play a role in DRM and CCA in each RWL and the actors' interactions, also identifying evaluation criteria for CCA/ DRM. The IAD focuses on key parameters of institutions, actor networks, multi-level interactions across administrative boundaries and vertical integration and governance modes. The analysis of institutions (e.g., regulations) and roles (e.g., catalysts, regional authority) will provide an overview of the enablers and barriers related to CCA/ DRM as institutions delimit capacity for social change. Having a good understanding of institutions is important because “they are intentional constructions that structure information and create incentives to act or not to act in a particular situation, thereby imposing constraints on the range of possible behaviour and feasible reforms. Interacting with physical and cultural conditions, institutions create incentives for social behaviour. This behaviour generates observable patterns of interaction, which in turn produce policy outcomes.” (Polski & Ostrom, 2017, p. 15)

In the context of DRM and CCA, we can assume that various systems in a systems-of-systems perspective, most notably actors and institutions, act as separate entities that interact and influence each other. In this environment, diverse actors (individuals and organisations), especially those outside of governmental organisations, take various roles (e.g., intermediary or facilitator) that define their decision-making power under multiple formal institutions (e.g., law, regulations, contracts) and informal ones (e.g., norms, collective agreements, coordination arrangements). The institutional analysis literature, mainly the Institutional Analysis and Development framework (IAD), supports the analysis of these constellations in the RWLs. The IAD provides a systematic way to analyse institutional structures, thus providing a basis for evaluating and comparing alternative governance mechanisms.

In summary, the IAD Framework is integral for understanding and developing the RTF, offering a comprehensive approach to analyse and evaluate the institutional structures, actor interactions, and governance mechanisms crucial for effective risk management in the context of DRM and CCA.

2.1.2 IRGC Risk Governance Framework

The first framework to begin conceptualising governance issues facing complex risks is the International Risk Governance Council (IRGC) Risk Governance Framework (2005; 2007), which refers to the components of risk governance as the totality of actors, rules, conventions, processes, and mechanisms concerned with how relevant risk information is collected, analysed, and communicated, and how regulatory decisions are taken. In particular, risk governance provides a conceptual and normative basis for dealing with uncertain, complex, and/or ambiguous risks (Klinke and Renn, 2012), and is thus well suited for disaster risk and climate adaptation, and systemic risk management.

Furthermore, the Framework's comprehensive, multi-disciplinary and multi-stakeholder approach helps in understanding, analysing and managing risk issues through outlining, and enhancing existing risk governance structures and processes. The Framework includes:

- **Four interlinked elements:** pre-assessment (identifying and framing risk issues), appraisal (assessing technical and perceived causes and consequences), characterisation and evaluation (making judgments about the risk), and management (deciding and implementing risk management options).
- **Three cross-cutting aspects:** stakeholder engagement, risk communication, and contextual understanding. These aspects are crucial for the holistic management of complex risks.

These components are analysed in detail hereafter.

Pre-assessment – identification and framing

The cyclical and iterative IRGC Risk Governance Framework begins with the phase of pre-assessment which refers to the identification of the breadth of issues that stakeholders and society may associate with a certain risk and the related benefits as well as existing indicators, routines, and conventions that may help to narrow down what is going to be addressed as risk and how it should be addressed.¹⁰ There are four components to the phase of pre-assessment, namely: (1) problem framing, (2) early warning, (3) screening, and (4) determination of scientific conventions. Based on these four components, the phase of pre-assessment clarifies the various perspectives on the identified risk(s), defines the issue to be looked at and forms the baseline for how the risk(s) is/are assessed and managed.

Appraisal – Assessing the technical and perceived causes and consequences of the risk

Risk appraisal is the next step in the risk governance process. Risk appraisal includes two major components, i.e., risk assessment and concern assessment. Risk assessment establishes the scientific link between risk agent(s) and consequence(s). The final output of risk assessment is the estimation of risk regarding probability distributions of modelled consequences. To achieve this goal, three core components have to be assessed: the identification and estimation of hazard, the appraisal of exposure and vulnerability, and the estimation of risk. Hence, risk estimation can take the form of quantitative or qualitative assessment. Concern assessment, the second component of risk appraisal, contributes an assessment of risk perceptions, societal concerns, and socio-political impacts of risk appraisal.

Characterisation and evaluation – Making a judgement about the risk and the need to manage it

The characterisation and evaluation phase consists of two components - knowledge characterisation and risk evaluation. In this phase, the decision must be made whether a risk is acceptable, tolerable, or intolerable. Acceptable activities offer benefits with negligible risks. Tolerable activities are pursued for their benefits, yet require additional risk reduction efforts. Intolerable activities need to be prohibited or substituted. Relevant evidence for making an informed choice on tolerability or acceptability is collected.

Risk evaluation applies societal values and norms to the judgement on tolerability and acceptability. Risk evaluation also determines the need for risk reduction measures.

Management – Deciding on and implementing risk management options

¹⁰ For the following see for instance:

IRGC. (2017). Introduction to the IRGC Risk Governance Framework. EPFL. <https://doi.org/10.5075/EPFL-IRGC-233739>

Renn, O. (2008). White Paper on Risk Governance: Toward an Integrative Framework. In O. Renn & K. Walker (Eds.), *Global Risk Governance. Concept and Practice Using the IRGC Framework* (pp. 3–76). Springer.

Schweizer, P.-J. (2021). Systemic risks – concepts and challenges for risk governance. *Journal of Risk Research*, 24(1), 78–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2019.1687574> IRGC, 2017; Schweizer, 2021

In this phase, all the information gathered in previous steps is combined. Especially the results of risk appraisal and tolerability and acceptability judgement are the basis for designing the appropriate risk management strategies. This phase consists of decision-making and implementation. Decision-making includes option identification and generation, option assessment, as well as option evaluation and selection. Option identification and generation discover potential management options for risk reduction. Option assessment investigates the future impact of each management option on economic, technical, social, political and cultural dimensions. Option evaluation assesses these options using multi-criteria analysis.

The second major part of the risk management phase deals with the implementation of the previously selected risk management option. Risk management implementation deals with option realisation, monitoring and control, as well as feedback from real-world risk management practice. Option realisation puts the chosen risk management option into practice. Monitoring and control observe its performance and whether it has the desired risk reduction effects. Feedback from real-world risk management practice then makes ex-post evaluation of the selected management option possible.

Figure 3: The IRGC Risk Governance Framework (IRGC, 2017, p.10).

Cross-cutting aspects – stakeholder engagement, risk communication context

Considering that risk management activities are implemented by a mix of public, private and civil society actors, the IRGC risk governance framework puts stakeholder engagement and communication at its core. Renn (2015) outlines the role of stakeholders in different phases of risk governance. During a pre-assessment phase the stakeholders can help to jointly frame the problem, define boundary conditions and set priorities by sharing their experiences and guidance on the process. For complex and systemic risk management, the establishment of

boundary conditions is crucial: it begins the process of outlining ‘the’ issue at hand and enables the examination of entry points for solution-making. This process will be further supported by other tools, as will be discussed later.

During the appraisal phase, stakeholder inputs will share knowledge in a wider sense to inform the limits of knowledge and the risks being evaluated and understand the associated impacts for different groups. During the characterisation/ evaluation phase, stakeholders will discuss any results from the risk assessment and broadly discuss the acceptability and tolerability of risk reduction measures. In other words, it helps identify options that are not only technologically or economically feasible, but humanly and ethically acceptable across all involved stakeholders (a priority discussed by Cosens, et al., 2021 in the context of governing complexity). During the management (decision-making and implementation) phase stakeholders can provide support to identify, assess, and select different management measures/ interventions.

Effective risk governance also requires the continuous process of risk communication. This involves the exchange or sharing of risk-related information, data, and knowledge among the diverse groups engaged in risk governance, such as scientists, policymakers, regulators, industry (including the insurance sector), consumers, and the general public (Florin & Parker, 2020). Risk communication and stakeholder engagement are distinct yet complementary processes supporting DRR and CCA. Effective communication is not a substitute for stakeholder involvement, it is a prerequisite, providing the knowledge base, allowing stakeholders to converse and become productive (Renn, 2015). Risk communication allows stakeholders to receive important information in a timely manner and can enable them to make informed contributions to the risk governance process by creating a deliberate two-way dialogue. Risk communication also involves explaining the rationale for decisions to wider stakeholders. Florin and Parker (2020) distinguish the goals of communication and its expected outcomes as literacy and behavioural change. Improving literacy through risk communication involves sharing information about the implications of the risks and related risk management measures, allowing recipients to build an understanding of the issues at stake. In many cases, risk communication approaches aim to go beyond the provision of information to changing behavioural patterns, such as the adjustment of existing risk management practices. As such, the IRGC Framework highlights that communication is needed throughout the process from risk assessment to all phases of risk management.

Figure 4: The risk management escalator and stakeholder involvement (Renn 2015).

Applications of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework and Lessons Learnt

The IRGC Risk Governance Framework has been applied retrospectively to various risk issues ranging from the governance of genetically modified crops (Tait, 2008) and nature-based tourism (Kuenzi & McNeely, 2008) to nanotechnology (Roco et al., 2008) and shipping risks in the Arctic (Goerlandt & Pelot, 2020). In the following, a brief overview will be provided for an application of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework that touches upon issues related to DIRECTED and the Project’s focus on hydrological extremes.

The Nagara River Estuary Barrage Conflict in Japan

In this case study, the IRGC Risk Governance Framework has been applied retrospectively to water resources management issues which challenged the disaster risk governance system in Japan (Okada et al., 2008, p. 221). The Nagara River Estuary Barrage was designed for flood control and protection of water supply. However, local fisher people became opposed to the barrage and were joined by environmentalists. Unreconcilable conflicts arose between government officials, local citizens, and representatives of civil society organisations. This conflict “represents an example of a problem in which decision-makers were faced with difficult trade-offs between protection of public safety and important water resources on the one hand, and concerns about adverse socio-economic and environmental impacts of the barrage on the other.” (Okada et al., 2008, p. 221) A key takeaway from the case study is that conflicts may evolve as the premises and values that dominated the decisions in the early planning stages changed over time, leading to a disconnect with the public’s attitudes and values.

The retrospective application of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework points towards the importance of “monitoring systems” for detecting emerging issues such as a shift in attitudes. Had there been an opportunity to identify, discuss and address these issues early in the project implementation, the ensuing lawsuits could have been avoided. Appropriate and “timelier implementation of the IRGC pre-assessment phase might have helped the conflict take a different path, leading to much faster resolution.” (Okada et al., 2008, p. 226) It is assumed

that the implementation of a concern assessment as specified by the IRGC Risk Governance Framework would have supported mutual understanding and provided venues for a more open-ended debate amongst opponents and proponents before the plan was decided and put into practice. Furthermore, the distinction between simple, complex, uncertain, and ambiguous risk issues provides guidance if risk issues evolve over time. Even though the project had been considered a simple risk issue at the beginning, adherence to the cyclical nature of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework would have made the governance process more adaptive to a change in contextual parameters.

Some critical reflections on the IRGC Risk Governance Framework:

Several points of critique have been voiced against the IRGC Risk Governance Framework of which we will mention those most relevant to the Framework's application in the DIRECTED Project.

First, the Framework seems to be too broad conceptually and lacking analytical detail for it to be directly used in concrete cases. However, the Framework is intended first and foremost as a “conceptual framework incorporating a set of key principles for sound risk governance.” (Renn & Walker, 2008a, p. 337) As such, it provides guidance on how risks may be investigated and how stakeholder and public engagement may be organised. This versatility serves the intents and purposes of DIRECTED as well as opening the opportunity to integrate other methodological advancements and frameworks, such as the Tandem framework and the Risk Layering approach, with the IRGC Risk Governance Framework.

Second, some commentators were unclear if the Framework should be applied as ex-ante guidance for decision-making and processes that precede or accompany risks or for an ex-post evaluation of specific cases. While the emphasis has primarily been on leveraging a more inclusive approach towards risk governance in governmental agencies and risk management programmes (Renn & Walker, 2008a, p. 339), several case studies have assessed the value of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework for retrospective analyses (see Renn & Walker, 2008b). For DIRECTED, the Framework will serve both purposes. The Framework serves as a yardstick for inclusive and participatory risk governance in the initial phase of the project and as a building block for a DIRECTED specific RTF. Through the application of the RTF in the RWLs, conclusions will be drawn as to current risk governance mechanisms in the RWLs. Furthermore, the RTF will be adapted to the specific needs in the RWLs and the project as a whole through an iterative approach.

In sum, the IRGC Risk Governance Framework serves in DIRECTED as both initial guidance for participatory risk governance and as a foundation for developing the tailored RTF. It represents a structured multi-dimensional approach to risk governance, where different aspects of risks are systematically addressed, and diverse inputs are valued to create a comprehensive risk management strategy, emphasizing stakeholder involvement and effective communication. Despite criticisms for being broad and conceptual, recent applications demonstrate its usefulness in addressing water management and disaster risk issues and highlight the importance of early identification and discussion of emerging issues.

2.1.3 SHIELD Model

Given these limitations of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework, and considering that it is a generic device, designed malleable enough to suit a range of risk-related problems from pandemics to accidents, there is a need to complement it with approaches specifically designed to support risk governance in the context of integrating DRM and CCA.

For this purpose, the SHIELD Model can provide insights as a set of guidelines for enhancing risk management capabilities developed through various research and participatory activities in the ESPRESSO Project - Enhancing Synergies for Disaster Prevention in the European Union (Lauta et al. 2018).¹¹ The model illustrates the interdependencies and interlinkage between management and governance in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/700342>

Change Adaptation (CCA). The approach takes a strong governance focus, recognising complex systems, and primarily targeting EU Member States and public officials/ institutions working on disaster risk and emergency management to enhance their risk management capabilities through disaster risk governance. It is framed around the Disaster Risk Management Cycle and its associated phases (i.e., response, recovery, prevention, preparedness) but recognises how these phases are dependent on various institutions, policies and structures and the need to support new sets of skills, such as cross-sectoral coordination and public engagement. The guidelines are organised around six themes, highlighting the key issues, associated recommendations and case study examples, as well as follow-up questions that form a checklist. The following list of themes is paraphrased from Lauterbach et al. (2018) emphasising their recommendations for integrating DRR and CCA:

- Sharing knowledge:
Siloed organisations, policy domains, and disciplines, result in limited sharing of knowledge across actors and disciplines and an overload of risk information that is not combined or aligned to meet the needs of specific DRM or CCA actors/ organisations. Recommendations include mapping of DRR and CCA knowledge actors, bridging gaps in science policy interface through intermediaries, facilitating knowledge sharing in diverse DRR and CCA networks, operational platforms or frameworks for collaboration, sharing DRR and CCA related data and information, and ensuring horizontal knowledge sharing across government sectors and vertically between national, regional and local levels.
- Harmonising capacities:
High-performing risk governance systems also require harmonised capacities across different skill levels to operate. They must also adapt to hazards, vulnerabilities and uncertainties. Recommendations include mapping existing technical/ material and human capacities, balance and matching them to climate and disaster risks, strengthening local partnerships and maintaining continuity by capturing synergies in DRR and CCA capabilities.
- Institutionalising coordination:
Holistic risk governance also requires institutionalised coordination, including mandates and cooperation mechanisms which can connect the levels of governance. Recommendations include clarifying mandates across climate, emergency and risk management agencies, encouraging flexibility to involve non-government and civil society actors affected by climate/ disaster risk, improving coordination through joint practical exercises or forums with DRR and CCA actors, and ensuring alignment of priorities, strategies, policies, mandates and terminology in DRR and CCA between public institutions.
- Engaging stakeholders:
Facing complex risks, traditional command-and-control approaches are inadequate. Thus, there is a need to expand the scope of stakeholders engaged. Recommendations include clarifying the role and responsibility of stakeholders for different tasks within DRR and CCA, communicating the value and mutual benefits for their participation, creating efficient and easily accessible web-based platforms for communication, utilising local knowledge and working through mediators.
- Leveraging investments:
Investing in the continuity of holistic risk management is central to reduce costs for response and recovery. However, in polycentric governance settings, it is often unclear who will bear the cost of risk reduction measures, and how to achieve long-term political commitment from all those involved. Recommendations include increasing the visibility of long-term DRR and CCA investments in terms of added-value, bridging connections between politicians and affected communities, and innovating within existing disaster risk financing structures to implement DRR and CCA strategies, nurturing partnerships with the private sector and government, providing consistent support for DRR and CCA investment beyond political election cycles, and capturing overlaps or synergies between DRR and CCA activities to increase efficient use of resources to implement plans and programmes.
- Developing communication:
Considering the abundance of information in our knowledge society, it is important to improve the communication of risk information with the public. This can also increase risk awareness among citizens and counteract poorly coordinated mass media coverage regarding emergencies. Recommendations to enhance communication

include creating multi-media platforms for risk awareness, cooperating with media partners, strengthening early warning platforms, innovating disaster and climate awareness campaigns beyond public messaging and bringing DRR and CCA education into schools and classrooms.

SHIELD Model Application – Integrating DRR and CCA into Irish emergency planning

The Model has been applied effectively for integration of DRR and CCA into emergency management in Ireland (Medway et al. 2022). Some of the key issues identified using the model were: the lack of awareness of the need to share knowledge; the risk of information overload; data and information as value; and knowledge silos. Although complimentary, CCA and DRR have different institutional structures and policies in Ireland, along with different norms and value systems, which require communication, coordination and collaboration to bridge. Poor vertical and horizontal coordination across levels and sectors working on emergency management and climate adaptation was found to negatively influence alignment between policies, funding and interventions.

SHIELD provided a useful framework for identifying key guiding actions based on the six pathways - see full details in (EPA, 2022). The application highlighted the need for a more inclusive approach that mainstreams socio-economic vulnerability data into risk assessment and planning processes subsequently strengthening participation in DRR and CCA by targeting engagement with vulnerable and marginalised groups. The need for a more joined-up government approach to capture synergies across investments in risk, adaptation and emergency management was also identified, such as pre-disaster recovery planning and social protection, as well as more research required around 'green budgeting' methods to incentivise integration.

Figure 5: The SHIELD Model revolving around the four disaster management phases (Lauta et al. 2018).

In summary, SHIELD is a comprehensive guidance tool to support DRR and CCA actors for holistically managing complex risks, bridging gaps between different risk management disciplines, and enhancing collaboration and coordination. The SHIELD model offers practical insights around key issues regarding DRR and CCA integration and useful guidance on the necessary steps to achieve more integration across DRR and CCA throughout Europe. However, there are limited insights into how this integration can be realised in specific real-world DRR/CCA settings. As such, the RTF is an opportunity to embrace the themes and learning from the SHIELD model around integrating DRM and CCA through its application and refinement in the RWLs. The themes and related checklists presented in the SHIELD Model offered useful guidance for the initial risk governance assessment in the RWLs and supported the conceptualisation of the RTF (as further explained in Section 3).

2.1.4 Risk Layering

The Risk Layering approach addresses some limitations of the above-described frameworks. Whilst they can help in framing the issues and opportunities for managing systemic risks, including outlining thematic focus areas requiring support or capacity, they fall short in detailing a suitable approach for identifying and managing systemic risks. In other words, they do not provide practical support for establishing boundary conditions, nor aid in the process of outlining entry points for risk management interventions in specific contexts. Thus, it is useful to look toward Risk Layering which can be used as either a fully probabilistic or storyline-based device to structure and examine complex risk issues.

Risk Layering builds on the legacy of quantification vis-à-vis unpredictability, an approach popular in risk-based approaches that focus on assessing damages and losses corresponding to hazards (Woo 2012). For example, the risk of losses due to natural hazard events is usually

conceptualized being a function of the hazard, the exposed elements as well the vulnerability of the exposed elements to the hazard (for a review of current approaches see Gill et al. 2022). Losses can be tangible or intangible, they can be measured in monetary terms based on market methods or not (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2023). For example, losses of assets such as houses that can be damaged by floods or earthquakes can be transformed into monetary terms, while biodiversity loss is more difficult to quantify in monetary terms (a quantitative approach could not ever fully encapsulate the centrality of biodiversity to human well-being and ecosystem stability). Furthermore, some of the natural hazard events will not cause any losses at all, while some will cause catastrophic losses. This may be due to various factors, including already implemented risk reduction measures or differences in the physical vulnerability of exposed elements (e.g., it is well known that fatalities are, on average, much higher in developing countries compared to developed countries, see CRED, UNISDR 2018).

In the special case where loss can be quantified in monetary terms and the risk of natural hazards can be determined in a probabilistic manner, a so-called Risk Layering approach can be applied (Hochrainer-Stigler and Reiter 2021). This approach aims to identify different Risk Layers, and to determine the most appropriate options for reducing risk in each layer (Mechler et al. 2014). For example, in the case of disasters, such Risk Layering uses hazard-recurrence data to identify appropriate interventions. The approach relies on the principle that different risk bearers or stakeholders—e.g., in households, businesses, and the public sector—are experiencing different contexts, and each of them should therefore adopt the most appropriate strategy given their risk exposure, the cost efficiency of the risk-mitigating solutions they can use, and their access to financing instruments. Hence, through Risk Layering individual risk measures, the most appropriate instruments to increase resilience can be identified (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Risk Layering approach for risk reduction and risk financing, based on analyzing loss distribution (i.e., a cumulative distribution function of losses). Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2020.

Depending on individual risk, the levels of losses (horizontal axis) are associated with the quantiles, or cumulative probabilities, of losses (left-hand vertical axis) according to the cumulative distribution function (blue curve) and with the expected return periods, or waiting times, separating the occurrence of events causing such levels or quantiles of losses (right-hand vertical axis). The transitions between risk reduction being more effective (yellow region), risk financing being more effective (orange region), and residual risk having to remain unprotected (red region) are illustrative and, depending on the studied risk, can take other, nonlinear shapes. Moving along the cumulative distribution function, the corresponding three intervals—alternatively expressed in terms of the levels, quantiles, or return periods of losses—can be read off (adapted from Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2020)).

For example, regarding events causing low-to-medium-sized losses, that happen relatively frequently, solutions are aimed at risk reduction—for instance, by enforcing rules that decrease asset exposure to hazards—typically are more cost-effective than solutions aiming at risk financing (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2021). The cost-effectiveness of potential solutions can be assessed using the mean and median of reduced losses, as in cost-benefit analyses (Mechler 2016). Because the costs of risk-reducing solutions often increase disproportionately with the severity of the events, other instruments are needed for larger disasters. Risk-financing instruments may thus become more cost-effective for disasters occurring with lower probability and higher impact that have debilitating consequences (catastrophic losses), which can be quantified by deviation measures and tail measures. Finally, as suggested by the uppermost layer in Figure 6, there is a point above which even financial instruments become too costly. These unmanaged risks are said to be residual and have to be left unprotected. This Risk Layering approach is readily extended from financial risks to non-financial risks.

Depending on their resilience, a stakeholder may or may not be able to cope with a particular hazard event. For example, a government may not be able to finance all infrastructure losses resulting from a disaster because of budget constraints (Hochrainer-Stigler et al. 2015). A firm may go out of business because of sudden changes in market conditions. Following the Risk Layering approach, we suggest that agents can identify their tipping points, i.e., the points in their loss distributions at which they would fail, and on this basis determine the most appropriate measures for decreasing their risk of failing. However, in dealing with systemic risks, these individual tipping points need to be managed together, because system collapses are triggered by individual failures which may be interdependent, and therefore must be analysed in conjunction. Whether an individual failure occurs, depends on the individual's resilience, which we suggest can be measured and enhanced using the Risk Layering approach. If an individual stakeholder is at risk, its failure has the potential to trigger systemic risks. How to assess and enhance systemic risk under these circumstances is based on the position of the exposed element within a socio-economic system and governance approach.

While the Risk Layer approach usually focuses on the quantification of risk, it can be used as a categorisation scheme for determining which perspective a given stakeholder focuses on, e.g., frequent, infrequent, or catastrophic events, as well as which management strategies are considered, e.g., risk reduction, risk financing or assistance. This categorization aids in connecting different governance scales and identifying overlaps, differences, and potential conflicts. Importantly, this simple categorisation can also be related to the **measurement**, modelling, and management of risks on different scales which may be interdependent and therefore need to be seen in conjunction. The entry point into the RTF for using a Risk Layer approach can arise at all steps within the IRGC framework as it is dependent on the stakeholder setting, e.g., focusing on emerging issues, on previous implemented options or new ways forward to provide a more integrative and holistic picture of the disaster landscape. Importantly, due to the divergent views of such options (models as well as policy processes), the feasible solution space must be implemented through a co-development process as exemplified within the RTF (see the discussion further down below).

Application: Risk Layering Application for Insurance

The Risk Layer approach was originally developed in the **insurance industry** and essentially follows an excess of loss approach to build up a risk transfer chain where reinsurer(s) compensate a primary insurer for losses exceeding a predetermined level. For example, a primary insurer only wants to cover losses up to a given maximum amount, say \$50 million. In case of exceedance of these losses they ask a reinsurer to step in. The reinsurer itself again wants to limit the maximum number of losses they would compensate, and only wants to cover losses up to a given limit, say \$250 million. They ask another reinsurer to step in if these losses are exceeded, and so on. For a given event, only the primary insurer or additionally reinsurers will pay part of the total losses, e.g., in case of an event which causes losses of \$30 million, only the primary insurer would be involved in the claim payments, in case of a \$150 million loss event, the primary insurer as well as the first reinsurer would step in for compensation, and so on. The Risk Layer can be related to the probabilities that such loss events are happening and therefore premiums based on the expected losses for each Risk Layer can be calculated.

One of the prerequisites for a Risk Layer approach is the possibility to quantify the risk in sufficient detail. For insurance purposes and other risk financing strategies (e.g., including contingent credits or catastrophe bonds) a full probabilistic representation, often in the form of a loss or exceedance distribution, is needed. Such quantification is not always possible (due to a variety of reasons including data limitation) and this limited the approach to specific risk problem settings in the past. However, recent advances have conceptualised Risk Layering within a broader setting (as discussed above) to include risk reduction, risk financing and assistance – even in the case that quantification is not possible (Mechler et al. 2014). The RTF takes this approach and extends it to provide a categorisation scheme that can be used for complex systems to govern risks on various scales, with various instruments and various decision-makers.

In practice, the RTF incorporates the Risk Layering approach to provide a more integrative and holistic understanding of disaster landscapes. It emphasizes co-development processes, ensuring diverse views on risk management options. The Model extends beyond just financial risks to include non-financial aspects, helping various stakeholders identify their tipping points and determine the most appropriate measures for decreasing their risk of failure. It especially can help bridging the gap between the more assessment related challenges and needs, and the more risk management related practices and strategies currently implemented or anticipated to be implemented in the future (Figure 8). Different risk measures as well as tangible and intangible dimensions can be selected for the assessment of risks which can feed into the modelling efforts to identify related risk management options. More importantly, the Risk Layer approach can be used as a categorization tool for identifying assessment needs of hazards and risks, as well as strategies to decrease them within a transdisciplinary way, including both natural and social related dimensions across a variety of different stakeholders. In essence, Risk Layering offers a versatile and practical tool for understanding and managing complex risks across different scales and contexts, enhancing the capacity to govern risks in a more integrated and holistic manner.

2.1.5 Premising the need for co-production for risk governance

Knowledge co-production is a central pillar of the RTF, beyond various risk governance tools, applied throughout the assessment and governance process of risks and disasters. Co-production, referred to as one of the ‘most important ideas in the theory and practice of knowledge and governance for global sustainability’ (Miller and Wyborn, 2020:88), can complement the application of various risk management approaches and tools. Indeed, as an evolving and iterative transdisciplinary collaboration process bridging actors in the interface of science, policy and practice, its self-conscious desire to avoid both social and techno-scientific determinism (Jasanoff, 2004) can simultaneously increase the accuracy of knowledge when describing risk issues whilst broaden the scope of available solutions.

For instance, if utilized to co-produce knowledge regarding systemic risk through the mapping of interdependencies, layers, networks or actors within a system and its sub-systems, it may produce more contextually accurate risk pictures by integrating ‘non-traditional’ ways of knowing. Using the language of systemic risk management, co-production can help to bridge the ‘data-policy gap’ (Sillmann, et al., 2022:20) by integrating the multiple languages and perspectives of actors to mitigate the fundamental differences in understanding, data collection methods, datasets and information sources used in describing risk.¹² This need is well-aligned with the ‘usability gap’ discussed in the context of climate services (Lemos, et al., 2012), which explains how useful climate information often goes unused since it is either not understood or does not match the needs of its users. Co-production can thus be used to patch data-policy and usability gaps by bridging participants and their knowledge systems together in a purposefully designed transdisciplinary knowledge integration setting supporting interoperability, collaboration, and communication (Daniels, et al., 2020).

¹² Linked to the issue of ambiguity and the plurality of legitimate viewpoints (Renn, et al., 2011)

Here, it should be noted that the language of co-production appears to align closely with the concept of ‘inclusive risk governance’ (Renn and Schweizer, 2009). However, whereas Renn and Schweizer (2009:175-183) discuss inclusive governance as the bridging of governments, the economic sector, scientific communities and ‘public values’ and continue to emphasize ‘scientific expertise, structured thinking, and excellent deliberative skills’ for risk management (p. 183), co-production emphasizes unstructured approaches and the value of information beyond expert-led innovation instead (Cosens, et al., 2021; Daniels, et al., 2020).¹³ Indeed, given that scientific discourses are often undemocratic by design (Latour, 2004) and act as self-referential machinery reproducing relationships of power (Foucault, 1980), it is more useful to look towards approaches that can adequately deconstruct the supremacy of expert knowledge in risk management.¹⁴ To exemplify this argument, one can investigate the issue of defining ‘vulnerability.’ As discussed by Faas (2016), those vulnerable are often represented with methods that erode their agency, discount the centrality of historical injustices, and most importantly, displace the perspectives of those affected by theorizing using expert narratives.

At its best, co-production may mitigate such divides if used as a self-conscious practice seeking to enforce democratic dialogue toward transformational change in systems and in terms of power relations – changes which would not take place if led by official committees and steering groups comprised of dominant members of society (including scientists) who are informally or formally committed to maintaining their preferred status quo (Cosens, et al., 2021). In the Foucauldian sense, the principle of co-production can also recognise itself as an elite discourse with roots embedded in hegemonic forms of knowing (Bevir, et al., 2019). Thus, it may use such self-awareness to expand the premise of ‘knowing’ by involving perspectives of those traditionally excluded from the operations of science. Those affected by the acts of governing are also likely to take an interest in decisions affecting them. Hence, by breaking the traditional boundaries between the governing and the governed through equal citizen engagement, methods of co-production can be leveraged to democratise (risk) governance (Berkes, 2017).¹⁵

For those who might find these arguments academic and overly postmodern, co-production can also diminish the gaps between generic and formal risk governance models. As pointed out by Boholm, et al., (2012) tools such as the IRGC Framework (or Risk Layering, for that matter) do not adequately encapsulate the realities and socially situated dynamics of practice that depend on the relationships between actors, institutional constraints and enablers, communication, problem-solving, and inter-organisational trust. Put simply, these mechanisms do not reach nor address social dynamics and hierarchies, whatever happens ‘behind the scenes’ when it comes to risk management. Consequently, by working to build trust and lasting relationships, and by improving knowledge integration and communication (Daniels, et al., 2020; Cosens, et al., 2021), co-production can be leveraged in between and within the tools and approaches of formal risk governance to address these ‘softer’ dimensions and deconstruct hierarchies of power by enforcing the principles of equality in stakeholder engagement.

Finally, co-production and associated social learning processes can be used to address the issue of system transformations toward resilience (Sillmann, et al., 2022; Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023). As has been recognised in research targeting complex socio-ecological systems (with a reference to the concept of resilience in particular), there is a need to leverage the systems’ non-linearities and processes of release (or collapse) and integrate learnings gathered from these to avoid reproducing unsafe conditions (Chaffin, 2022; Gunderson, 2010; Cosens, et al., 2021). Understanding and mapping these interdependencies is essential for monitoring and adjusting the adaptive management of a system (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023) and is a cornerstone for learning toward transformations (Cosens, et al., 2021). The latter is particularly important; where some emphasize refocusing the loci of system boundaries toward clarifying what is both inside and outside of a hypothesized system, including the root causes of systemic risks (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2023), others have pointed out that this process hinges upon the notion of unlearning of reductionist habits

¹³ I.e., appearing to emphasize the knowledge of experts vis-à-vis ‘values’ of politicians (p.180) and ‘values’ of the public (p.183)

¹⁴ And more centrally, address their inability to admit shortfalls in describing ‘reality’ or investigating themselves as elite discourses.

¹⁵ In alignment with its roots in 1970s deliberative democracy.

(Rogers, et al., 2013; Berkes, 2017).¹⁶ In relation to the earlier arguments regarding the tendency of systems discourse to depoliticise and naturalise systems under their inspection (Walker and Cooper, 2011), it is also important to interrogate the underlying assumptions, ideologies and discursive practices embedded in the management of systemic risks.

In acknowledgement of these issues, one can, in theory, leverage co-production to not only co-explore systemic risks, but use it to inform all involved stakeholders via the exchange of divergent perspectives to support transdisciplinary knowledge production in an unstructured manner. Indeed, given that the desire for stability often provides a sense of security, and thus favours the status quo (Cosens, et al., 2021), all previously set research agendas or ‘superior’ methods soothing this desire, risk reinforcing a normative reliance on themselves (and inhibit the potential for transformational change through the unexpected). Therefore, learning must be framed as an ongoing, adaptive process that fosters critical reflection and the constant synthesis of knowledge toward transformations (Kruse, et al., 2017). To this end, collective and dialogic problem-solving, reflexive practices, improvisation and adaptation are features of social learning that can be facilitated by co-productive approaches (Slater and Robinson, 2020). If seeking transformational systems change, transdisciplinary co-production can thus be leveraged to broaden the scope of selected discourses and disciplines beyond normative narratives whilst addressing issues such as hierarchies of power and expert-led governing.

In summary, **co-production is a central aspect of the RTF**, emphasizing the collaborative creation of knowledge and decision-making in risk governance. It is seen as crucial for integrating various perspectives and knowledge systems, particularly for systemic risk management. Co-production helps bridge gaps between data and policy by addressing usability issues through utilizing stakeholders’ involvement in the knowledge-creation process. This approach differs from traditional expert-led models by valuing diverse inputs and perspectives, aiming to democratize risk governance. The application of co-production can enhance understanding and management of complex risks by incorporating ‘non-traditional’ knowledge and addressing social dynamics often overlooked by formal risk governance models. It fosters trust, improves communication, and deconstructs power hierarchies, making stakeholder engagement more equitable. Co-production also supports system transformations towards resilience, encouraging critical reflection and adaptive learning.

2.1.6 Structuring co-production through the Tandem Framework

Despite its popularity and widespread usage, confusion remains as to what, precisely, is meant by the term “co-production”, and how to apply it effectively (Miller and Wyborn, 2020), as well as how co-production can best capture the socio-political dimensions underpinning the process (Turnhout, et al., 2020). To address these issues under DIRECTED, the Stockholm Environment Institute’s **Tandem Framework** (Daniels, et al., 2020; Bharwani, et al., 2024) has been selected to provide a non-prescriptive guide to co-production that seeks to handle these challenges head-on.

¹⁶ The point of adaptive governance; admitting uncertainty and coping with it.

Figure 7: The Tandem Framework for transdisciplinary knowledge co-production (Bharwani, et al., 2024).

Initially designed to support the co-production of climate services, Tandem seeks to address the gaps between science and policy by facilitating and guiding equal, iterative, and non-structured collaboration for knowledge co-production whilst responding to the needs of the social context. By focusing on stakeholder engagement beyond ‘products’ to ‘process’, it also seeks to improve the coordination, collaboration, and communication between stakeholders (such as policymakers, planners, researchers, engineers, or modellers), and guide co-working by focusing on relationships and trust. Tandem also provides structure in conceptualising and implementing co-production amidst a vague field of literature – a limitation that often hinders its application to practice (Bandola-Gill, et al, 2022). The process has been divided into iterative phases that can be adapted to local context and needs based on associated guiding questions (Bharwani et al., 2024). These will be further discussed within the next section, in relation to the proposed RTF.

Beyond the framework, presumed benefits of knowledge co-production are also worth reiterating here. For instance, if utilized to co-produce knowledge regarding systemic risk through the mapping of interdependencies, layers, networks or actors within a system and its sub-systems, it may produce more contextually accurate risk pictures by integrating ‘non-traditional’ ways of knowing (Hochrainer-Stigler, et al., 2024). Using the language of systemic risk management, co-production can help to bridge the ‘data-policy gap’ (Sillmann, et al., 2022:20) by integrating the multiple languages and perspectives of actors to mitigate the fundamental differences in understanding, data collection methods, datasets and information sources used in describing risk. This need is well-aligned with the ‘usability gap’ discussed in the context of climate services (Lemos, et al., 2012), which explains how useful climate information often goes unused since it is either not understood or does not match the needs of its users. Knowledge co-production can thus be used to patch data-policy and usability gaps by bridging participants and their knowledge systems together in a purposefully designed transdisciplinary knowledge integration setting supporting interoperability, collaboration, and communication (Daniels, et al., 2020; Bharwani et al., 2024). In a manner of speaking, co-production under the RTF thus represents a mode of research seeking to create a more inclusive, socially robust and deliberative approach seeking to respond to contextual

challenges (Verwoerd, et al., 2022; Nordström, et al., 2020), structured via the application of the Tandem framework.

The process has been divided into **iterative phases** (Figure 7), which can be adapted to the local context and needs. It begins with an optional phase, dedicated to scoping and reviewing vulnerabilities, risks, challenges and decision context, with a particular focus on exploring the climate or disaster risks perceived as most pressing among the selected stakeholders. Vulnerabilities, different knowledge systems and wider socioeconomic concerns may all be a part of this unstructured assessment phase, founding the application of the Framework steps. Following this initial stage, one may begin:

1. **Scope, review, identify and engage**, this forms the first element of the Tandem process, to scope and review climate and non-climate risks, vulnerabilities and impacts, as well as identify and engage stakeholders who may contribute to the issue at hand, including sectoral, institutional, and local actors. It also focuses on champions, change agents and those affected by decision-making, in efforts to accommodate the perspectives of those vulnerable and subject to acts of governing to support knowledge integration beyond expert narratives.
2. **Co-exploring** focuses on understanding the **risk governance context**, i.e., the risk-related challenges that could be addressed via improved decision-making, improved access and use of risk information, and the scale of risks in their spatial and temporal dimensions. Furthermore, it is useful to begin identifying and co-exploring key challenges and common goals with stakeholders affected by risks (and decision-making). As needed, one may return to the first element as knowledge of challenges and goals increases to broaden the scope of engagement to guarantee that the knowledge, expertise and lived experience of participants selected to take part in the decision-making process reflect the issues at hand. Depending on the priorities of the stakeholders, co-exploration may focus on risks and the governance context, information needs and data, and/or specific hazard-related issues.
3. **Co-design** begins with identification and appraisal of solutions considering uncertainty, maladaptation, compound and cascading risks, synergies, trade-offs and co-benefits. (Bharwani, et al., 2024). It guides activities and engagements to dig deeper into these needs through co-production, by aiding and deconstructing underlying assumptions embedded in the data itself and supporting the distillation of information in a manner that is easily accessible to all involved.
4. **Integrating new knowledge and partners** aims at co-developing the capacities of both service providers as well as their users, in efforts to integrate co-produced knowledge and solutions, and to solidify partnerships between them toward lasting collaboration (Bharwani, et al., 2024). This emphasizes the identification of early actions that could be implemented, within a specific time frame, and what methods and approaches are suitable for their implementation. Data needs, financing, or support for communication and decision-making can all form a part of this stage. Synergies, trade-offs and co-benefits should also be considered.

Enhancing legacy and sustainability. This ongoing objective and ambition aim to institutionalize knowledge co-production processes in existing governance structures (with an emphasis on funding, communication, partnership and capacity development) to support the ownership, legacy and sustainability of resilient development beyond the lifetime of the project (Bharwani, et al., 2024).

With this set of approaches in mind, the RTF integrates the best-suited aspects of them to establish a comprehensive approach for addressing complex real-world challenges. The frameworks selected for the RTF share similarities, synergies, and potential to fill gaps that each alone would leave behind. By adapting and incorporating components from each of these, we propose a solution that can simultaneously aid in identifying and outlining complex risk issues, determining entry points for their management, as well as supporting and exploring governance settings and mechanisms to promote the practical operationalisation and institutionalisation of these ambitions beyond the DIRECTED Project. In addition, to move beyond an expert-led, top-down, and process-based mechanism that rarely aligns well with real-world challenges (e.g., hindered by lack of communication, limited trust and misaligned knowledge systems), co-production will be introduced as the key component – a glue – with which it is possible to tie together operational principles in a manner that encourages their exploration and implementation through transdisciplinary collaboration.

3.1 Combining existing frameworks

The frameworks are combined as follows. Acknowledging the IRGC Risk Governance Framework's core commitments to communication, stakeholder engagement and context, the Tandem Framework will be introduced as a process to mainstream the principles of co-production in a structured manner within all IRGC phases from risk pre-assessment to their management. In other words, Tandem will be used to apply 'traditional' risk governance approaches (including problem-framing tools such as Risk Layering and multi-risk methodologies) with a commitment to non-hierarchical and non-structured transdisciplinary collaboration that encourages engagement, innovation, and commitment to the local risk governance context. In addition, the logical synergies between these two frameworks will be leveraged to maintain internal coherence. For example, the process of scoping, identifying relevant stakeholders and co-exploring the (risk) context aligns well with the phases of 'pre-assessment' and 'appraisal', seeking to frame the problem and characterise risks, respectively. By leveraging these frameworks, and focusing on elaborating systemic risks, the outputs are more likely to produce contextually accurate risk information, applicable to the RWL stakeholders. Within these, Risk Layering can be used as a storyline-based structuring device, in efforts to maintain the momentum of co-production toward DIRECTED ambitions. It especially can identify how the more risk assessment related needs can be aligned with already established and envisioned risk management practices (Figure 8).

Similarly, it is possible to align the Tandem stages of exploring capacity development needs and identifying solutions with the IRGC phases of characterisation and management, comprising the outlining of risk reduction options, judging the tolerability or acceptability of the selected measures, and option identification and assessments. These are also flexible enough to accommodate contextual priorities, as determined by the participants throughout the co-production process. For management, it is also useful to leverage Tandem phases, in efforts to integrate knowledge, distilling relevant information and data, and making it accessible to stakeholders is central for supporting the implementation of selected risk management solutions.

As previously indicated, the Risk Layering approach was initially developed within insurance applications (Hochrainer-Stigler and Reiter 2021). Already here one can implicitly distinguish between frequent and infrequent events as the primary insurer usually focuses on smaller losses which occur with higher frequencies and transfers more infrequent events with larger corresponding losses to reinsurers. Losses from rare but catastrophic (very extreme) events cannot be managed through insurance and assistance is needed, e.g., the government steps in as an insurer of last resort. Not only risk financing, but also risk reduction can be included in such Risk Layering approaches with the assumption that risk reduction may be especially useful for tackling frequent risks (Linnerooth-Bayer and Hochrainer-Stigler 2015). The Risk Layer approach was expanded to include different types of risk management options, especially risk reduction, risk financing and assistance for different layers of risk (Mechler et al. 2014). For each of these Risk Layers, different risk metrics may be used to represent such kind of events. For example, for frequent events one may use average losses while for infrequent events one may use Tail measures (such as "Value at Risk", that is, the maximum level of loss that is likely to occur in a certain period) or Expected Shortfall (such as "Conditional Value at Risk", that is, the expected value of the part of the focused random variable that exceeds a certain threshold). Sometimes these events cannot be quantified but are seen by the risk bearer to belong to a given category, both in terms of events/risks as well as instruments to reduce them (Figure 8). As indicated within Figure 8, the Risk Layering approach can relate the risk assessment with the risk management part and therefore also provides ways forward how to bridge the gap between these two.

	Risk Reduction	Risk Financing	Assistance
Frequent events			
Infrequent events			
Extreme events			

Figure 8: General categorization scheme of the Risk Layering Approach to position stakeholders’ current Risk Layer and management options.

The Risk Layering and general categorisation scheme shown above can be applied to all the IRGC Risk Governance Framework’s steps within the RTF and can be related not only to quantitative dimensions (models and data across scales), but also to governance processes and policies. It also highlights possible frictions, overlaps, and gaps across different stakeholders. In that regard, the question of how an event cannot be coped with, either due to the lack of risk management measures or insufficient resources, may have an effect on risks of different stakeholders, and could be utilized to expose previously unforeseen gaps.

Finally, this proposed configuration will be aligned with the SHIELD Model, which provides thematic focus areas and capabilities to guide the integration of DRR and CCA across the four different phases of the DRM cycle from response to recovery, prevention, and preparedness. It also provides practical guidance on issues such as mapping the field of relevant actors, leveraging cross-sectoral investments, balancing national and local scales, exploring coordination mandates, mapping of capacities, and so on – methods that are otherwise absent from the IRGC and Tandem frameworks. Taken together, these approaches can thus form a foundation for managing complex and systemic risks, beginning from the principles of co-production, expanding towards risk governance and multi-level collaboration, fit for the European context. Figure 9 visualizes how the Framework, approaches and processes – IRGC Risk Governance Framework, Tandem, Risk Layering and SHIELD – connect and complement one other, with stakeholder engagement and co-production as the common thread helping to integrate them all.

Figure 9: Combining existing frameworks - IRGC, SHIELD, Tandem and Risk Layering.

In synthesis, the integration of selected frameworks within the RTF aims to create a **comprehensive approach to risk governance**. It combines the **IRGC** risk governance framework's focus on communication and stakeholder engagement with the **Tandem** Framework's structured co-production process. This integration enhances effective application of traditional risk governance tools, such as Risk Layering and multi-risk methodologies, in a collaborative and non-hierarchical manner. The **Risk Layering approach**, originally developed for insurance applications, helps categorize different types of risks and management options. This approach is expanded to include risk reduction and financing strategies for various risk levels. The SHIELD Model adds practical guidance on integrating DRR and CCA across different DRM cycle phases. Together, these frameworks form a **foundation for managing complex and systemic risks**, emphasizing principles of co-production, multi-level collaboration, and stakeholder engagement to suit the European context.

3.2 The emerging new Risk-Tandem Framework

This conceptual overlay has been used to form the RTF, by seeking to harmonize these different models in a more concise and approachable manner, with an emphasis on the DIRECTED aims regarding the interoperability of data and governance systems.

It is comprised of two main components represented in Figure 10. Firstly, the more conceptual framing facilitates the combination of risk governance approaches and knowledge co-production processes, represented through incoming spirals that form the RTF with stakeholder engagement at its core connecting both sides. Secondly, the inner blue the RTF is expanded out to provide detail on the different layers of the Framework. Stakeholder engagement is placed at the centre considering the connection between the SHIELD Model theme on engaging stakeholders, the IRGC Risk Governance Framework's focus on stakeholder engagement and Tandem Step 1. The next orange circle shows the steps of the Tandem process, surrounded by the phases of the IRGC Risk Governance Framework, which will embed Risk Layering and the general categorisation scheme as part of the analysis and co-production process.

In the outer green circle, some of the SHIELD themes have been restructured to better align with the RTF, but its principles and guiding questions will continue to apply. Generating knowledge on risk governance and facilitating knowledge co-production in the RWLs helps in identifying areas for alignment between different modelling platforms, tools and their sources of data. In this regard, the application of the RTF in the RWLs does not only serve as a “proof of concept”, but also the possibility to adapt and improve the Framework. As such, there is scope to expand the sharing knowledge component under SHIELD to embed aspects pertaining to data, modelling, information interoperability, and the Data Fabric, the central federated data and model platform handled in DIRECTED Work Package 5.¹⁷

The Framework can identify the key entry points for embedding and sustaining the outputs and solutions generated through the knowledge co-production process and the wider DIRECTED activities into practice or policy. This can relate to improving risk governance and knowledge co-production through improved communication and coordination, model/data/information interoperability, financing and resources distribution or mobilisation, and developing or sustaining institutional capacity and skills for DRR and CCA. For example, in the RWLs, this could mean operationalising the Data Fabric into the way they conduct risk assessment or mapping, utilising policy briefs for strategic advocacy, committing to sustaining a science-practice partnership or forum or embedding a new training programme.

¹⁷ The Data Fabric sets out to develop a reference architecture for the data infrastructure, services and capabilities required to achieve the vision of Interoperability for DRM and CCA. As stated in the DIRECTED Grant Agreement, the objective of Work Package 5 (in collaboration with other WPs), is to “[D]evelop the high-level architectural definition for the Data Fabric implementation required to support DDR and CCA Interoperability...” and “[U]ndertake the configuration of a prototype covering the Use Cases defined within the RWLs...” (see DIRECTED Grant Agreement page 12, for more information)

Figure 10: The Risk-Tandem Framework.

3.3 Monitoring, evaluating, and learning through the Risk-Tandem Framework

Throughout the implementation of the RTF there is a continuous process of reflection, and as such, monitoring, evaluation, and learning are visualised as circling components around the RTF (Figure 10). This process is a central piece of Tasks 1.3 and 3.3 where Task 1.3 entails “[evaluating] the RTF’s performance in the RWLs. The task will be carried out in parallel to T3.3” (DIRECTED Grant Agreement, p. 8). Accordingly, Task 3.3 is outlined in two steps: “First, we will test the hypotheses developed in T3.2 and where possible apply recommendations for improving governance in the RWLs. [...] Second, we will update and improve the RTF based on empirical evidence generated in RWLs by means of interviews and multi-stakeholder workshops” (DIRECTED Grant Agreement, p. 10).

The RTF involves monitoring, evaluating and learning (MEL) around a set of indicators focusing on multiple dimensions, such as outcomes of training and capacity development with RWLs, the outcomes of plans and risk management solutions designed and implemented by RWL stakeholders and the effectiveness of the governance mechanisms in strengthening multi-stakeholder engagement, facilitating interoperability, and stimulating knowledge exchange.

There is a strong body of literature on governance evaluation from the fields of risk and environmental management. For example, Alexander et al. (2016) identifies criteria for evaluating flood risk governance, including societal resilience (capacity to resist, absorb, recover, and adapt), resource efficiency, and legitimacy (social equity, accountability, transparency, participation, access to information, procedural justice, acceptability). Similarly, the OECD Principles of Water Governance use criteria on effectiveness (capacity, policy coherence, scales, roles and responsibilities), efficiency (data/ information, financing, regulation, innovation), and trust and engagement (integrity/ transparency, stakeholder engagement, trade-offs, monitoring and evaluation) to evaluate water and related risk governance structures (Akhmouch et al. 2016). Further in the water resources domain, Carr et al. (2012) outline three main evaluation methods for measuring effective stakeholder participation through (1) Process evaluations, (2) Intermediary outcome evaluations, and (3) Resource management outcome evaluations. Within the climate adaptation and risk governance scholarship, social learning is used as an evaluative indicator for successful stakeholder engagement and used to evaluate specific risk governance mechanisms, such as partnerships. For example, Benson et al. (2016) evaluated social learning in the Regional Flood and Coastal Committees in England.

The concept of accountability is used across governance and legal literature as an intertwined indicator and mechanism for understanding and evaluating risk governance and stakeholder engagement. Accountability can elaborate standards for the evaluation of the behaviour of (public) actors (such as transparency, decision-making rules and stakeholder participation), but can also be seen as a mechanism i.e., an institutional relationship or arrangement in which an agent can be held to account by another agent or institution (Bovens, 2010). Accountability mechanisms, and potential sanctions, do not need to be only legal in nature. Bovens (2007) argues that multiple mechanisms for accountability exist: political (e.g., accountability of elected representatives), legal (e.g., courts and judicial processes), administrative, professional (e.g., public inquiry and professional bodies), and social forms (e.g., community participation and publicity). Accountability mechanisms and resulting processes enable policymakers and administrators to reflect on and learn from the successes and failures of their policies (Bovens, 2007).

Furthermore, procedural rights are of particular importance in environmental, risk, and climate issues as they place the participation and empowerment of local communities at the heart of the policy-making processes. The procedural right to access information, public participation, and access justice are recognised as rights under international law, for example as set out in Principle 10 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (1992). Such rights intersect with the concept of accountability since they can hold actors to account and can enable or hinder stakeholder engagement processes and resulting policy outcomes. In the

context of the RTF, the availability and effectiveness of such accountability mechanisms and procedural rights can be assessed as part of the risk governance analysis. Where deemed most appropriate, accountability can be used to evaluate the outcomes and impact of stakeholder engagement and knowledge co-production processes and any resulting governance mechanisms in the RWLs.

Importantly, indicators such as participation and inclusion play a central role for the MEL aspects of the RTF. In line with the ethics recommendations set forth in WP 8, Deliverable 8.2, we underline the importance of positive bias, i.e., actively amplifying the voices of historically marginalized groups in the decision-making process. From a conceptual perspective, this is highlighted in the following analytical framing, specifically in steps 2,3, and 4. Practically speaking, the DIRECTED project seeks to create safer spaces of discussion and deliberation, as well as guide the RWLs in creating such spaces themselves through workshops and presentations (see Annex III).

Given the dynamic and contextual nature of the RTF, it would be counterproductive to provide a static set of indicators. While tried and tested indicators from the existing approaches (e.g., SHIELD and the vulnerability index, or the IRGC's list of indicators) serve as a baseline and are presented to the RWLs, the innovative methodology of the RTF is based on its co-creative and context-sensitive application process. We have therefore developed an analytical lens in order to enable WP 3 to both assess and evaluate the risk governance processes found in the various RWLs, while also basing the application of the RTF on the various needs through the RWLs. Accordingly, this lens then also serves as a starting point for the exact assessment of indicators for the monitoring, evaluation, and learning phase.

1. **First, the RTF asks how the institutional structures within the RWLs are influenced by the formal and informal rules that reproduce, inhibit, or facilitate various decisions and interactions.** This framing builds on the Institutional Analysis and Development Framework (Ostrom 2010; Poski & Ostrom 2017). The Risk-Tandem Framework conceptualizes institutions as a repetition of decisions made under the influence of a set of formal and informal rules. Further, these repeated decisions are assumed to be made in line with a specific outcome or goal that the institution seeks to achieve. This conceptualization allows for the assessment of the decision-structures found throughout the various RWLs. It also highlights the importance of informal and formal procedures that underpin each decision made in the context of DRR and CCA within the RWLs. On this basis, the formal and informal rules guiding the decision process, as well as the various goals, become a first set of indicators for the assessment and management of risk strategies in the RWLs.

Indicators: Institutional Context	Description	Relation to T3.1/Risk-Tandem Framework
Formal Rules	Understanding the formal rules in place (laws; norms; requirements; hierarchies; etc.)	Essential for governance baseline assessment, which forms part of T3.1 and T3.2.
Informal Rules	Understanding the informal rules in place (unwritten rules and norms of behavior; modes of 'getting things done'; historical contexts.	Essential for governance baseline assessment, which forms part of T3.1 and T3.2.

Table 1: Indicators: Institutional Context.

2. **Second, the RTF asks what kind of risk governance strategies the RWLs currently employ, and identifies normative and ethical challenges that carry practical implications of feasibility.** These analytical viewpoints build on the IRGC Risk Governance Framework (IRGC 2005; 2007). In a first step, answering these two questions requires insight into the generation and evaluation process of various risks relevant to the RWLs, i.e., understanding the risks at hand. This allows for the second step, namely where possible improving or learning from the decision-making and management process followed by the RWLs.

Indicators: Risk Governance	Description	Relation to T3.1/Risk-Tandem Framework
Feasibility	Whether an action can be done (politically, economically, etc.)	To what degree can DIRECTED suggest certain changes / what are the barriers.
Inclusivity/ Equity	Is there active and equitable inclusion of all participants and stakeholders? This entails meaningful participation beyond mere tokenism.	Certain assumptions of participatory and procedural justice are a prerequisite for the application of the RTF.
Accountability	What are the structural and informal forms of accountability?	Accountability is closely linked to who can and should be held responsible for certain procedures, highlighting who the relevant stakeholders are in each situation.

Table 2: Indicators: Risk Governance.

3. **Third, the RTF looks to identify the possible linkages among various stakeholders throughout both the DRR and CCA structures found in the RWLs.** Aspect number three is founded in the SHIELD model (Lauta et al. 2018). This also complements the broader questions surrounding risk governance strategies in general mentioned in two (2). Accordingly, the RTF seeks to synergize efforts throughout the Risk Management process, such as guiding investments towards complimentary effects with regards to DRR and CCA. This holistic view also entails actively engaging with potentially marginalized,

and/or socio-economically disenfranchised and vulnerable communities, to better integrate their needs and challenges.

Indicators: Goals & Aims	Description	Relation to T3.1/Risk-Tandem Framework
Goals & Aims	Identifying overlapping interests and goals among DRR and CCA related plans and measures	Understanding that aims/goals of varying actors may differ or overlap will prove as a central leverage point for both the assessment and improvement of the RWLs decision-making process, which is one of the aims of Task 3.1
Participation	Stakeholder participation (identifying vulnerable groups and defining social vulnerability)	Related to the indicators mentioned in (2), stakeholder participation is a crucial aspect of the RTF. In contrast to (2) however, participation here is merely framed as a quantitative criterion (who and how many people are involved), rather than focusing on the e.g., socio-economic context highlighted above
Synergies and trade-offs across actions/ measures	Maximizing synergies and managing tradeoffs across DRM and CCA measures	

Table 3: Indicators: Goals & Aims.

4. **Fourth, the RTF enables users to establish the boundary conditions which delineate the various systems and structures potentially threatened by a given disaster.** Here, the RTF relies and expand on the Risk Layering approach (Woo 2012; Hochrainer-Stigler 2023), in which disasters of different return periods are identified as boundary conditions according to the risk perception and risk addressing abilities of relevant stakeholders. This method links different risk management measures to correspondent level of disaster risks.

Indicators: Risk Management & Systems Boundaries	Description	Relation to T3.1/Risk-Tandem Framework
Return period of disasters	Return periods of 1 year, 10 years, 100 years, etc.	Understanding the disaster-scale which the RWLs plan to manage is crucial for governance
Risk perception of various stakeholders	How much and to whom do these risks matter? And what are the potential impacts if they manifest?	Knowing how risks are perceived throughout the RWLs helps tune the RTF to the relevant needs, fulfill the requirement of robust inclusion, and understand the various risk drivers better

Risk addressing capabilities	What measures can be adopted by whom? What financing resources are available to implement these measures? What agreement can be achieved between different stakeholders?	Assessing the ability of addressing risks supports developing risk management strategies collaboratively and comprehensively
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Table 4: Indicators: Risk Management & System Boundaries.

5. **Fifth, the RTF seeks to enable, improve and learn from knowledge co-production processes through training of trainers. Its application will also support in uncovering and co-exploring issues as outlined above in RWL contexts.** Its application is based on the co-production approach (Norström, et al., 2020; Turnhout, et al., 2020; Daniels, et al., 2020; Miller and Wyborn, 2020), and structured through the Tandem framework that form the core of the Risk-Tandem phases (Bharwani et al. 2024). Informed by the WP 4 MEL strategy for Training of Trainers, and the MEL for assessing knowledge co-production outcomes (see Section 5 of D1.2. Capacity Development Strategy for details), the indicators for assessing knowledge co-production processes are developed separately. However, they will be linked to MEL as envisaged under Risk-Tandem, in an effort to explain the quality of co-production processes and effects of training to risk governance outcomes.

Indicators: Co-production	Description	Relation to T3.1/Risk-Tandem Framework
Stakeholder needs	What are the needs/interests of the various stakeholders	Given the RTF’s co-productive foundation, it can only function with active input from the RWL’s and their respective needs.
Level of knowledge co-production	To what degree is co-creation within the RWLs enabled, and to what extent do the RWLs foster co-creation outside the interactions with DIRECTED	With co-creation being such a central aspect of the RTF, finding ways to assess the levels of co-creation in the RWLs is crucial in order to measure progress.

Table 5: Indicators: co-production.

Based on this conceptual lens and the indicators, WP 4 (in close collaboration with WP 3) is measuring the impacts and outcomes of training activities for Trainers and RWL hosts (such as, satisfaction, perception, and implementation of co-production in RWLs). The other – and more complex – MEL dimensions involve assessing how well trainers have translated knowledge gained in action, and how they have been used to build relationships, trust, and communication. In a complimentary manner, WP 3 assess new governance mechanisms, plans, policies, and/or integrated databases within the RWL.

In order to continuously monitor progress, an outline has been designed detailing the inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts for systematic monitoring and evaluation of the project impacts for each RWL. The impact assessment is done through a range of methods such as quantitative and qualitative assessment of KPIs, storytelling, and documenting evidence of improved policy and practice.

In essence, the RTF emphasizes ongoing evaluation and adaptation to effectively manage risks, by assessing the Framework’s impact and effectiveness in improving stakeholder engagement and fostering collaborative knowledge creation. The goal is to develop a responsive and contextually relevant approach to risk governance, ensuring that the solutions devised are well-suited to the specific challenges encountered in real-world settings.

3.4 Application of the Risk-Tandem Framework in the RWLs

The Risk-Tandem is designed to be applied by a range of actors through an iterative, step by step process that supports local ownership (evolving based on practical lessons, increasing capacity and confidence gained through co-exploring challenges and relevant data). In DIRECTED, the RTF is being applied and refined in RWL contexts in a phased approach during the project with an emphasis on continuous monitoring, learning and evaluation and supporting change over time.

Four phases – **Foundation, Growth, Learn and Sustain** - are identified for Risk-Tandem implementation in RWLs as visualised in Figure 11 over the project’s 4-year timeline and connected through monitoring, learning and evaluation.

The objective of this section is to demonstrate the completed activities and plans towards the application of Risk-Tandem as part of Task 3.2 within each of these application phases. The Foundation Phase (Year 1) involved familiarising RWL hosts with Risk-Tandem, strengthening relationships for engagement, supporting on initial risk governance analysis and providing knowledge co-production training. The detailed guidance documents and related activities in this phase are presented in the following sub-section 3.4.1 as these were completed alongside the development of the Risk-Tandem conceptual development as presented in this Deliverable 3.1. Plans for Risk-Tandem applications and related activities and training in the Growth, Learn and Sustain phases are presented in the following sub-sections.

A final version of Risk-Tandem will emerge based on the **practical lessons and insights** gained through the RWL applications (Task 3.2) to support wider applications by other stakeholders working on DRR and CCA. Task 3.3 (in parallel with Task 1.3) will focus on evaluating the updated RTF’s performance in the RWLs and providing guidance and recommendations.

Figure 11: Application of Risk-Tandem in RWLs through four phases as part of Task 3.2.

3.4.1 Phase 1: Foundation

The Foundation phase is focused on supporting RWLs to understand the initial RTF and strengthen the relationships for engagement in the RWLs, including among the consortium partners and with their RWL stakeholder groups. This involves supporting RWLs to conduct an initial analysis of the risk governance setting and context through the lens of Risk-Tandem and training activities to strengthen RWL hosts' capacity for knowledge co-production and understanding of DRR and CCA complex systems (see further details in the Capacity Development Strategy D1.2). Below the different Foundation Phase activities done in collaboration with WP 3 and WP 4 are described, along with a short reflection on their application in the RWL.

Stakeholder identification and mapping support

As part of Task 1.1 the RWL hosts established their RWLs through signing agreements with a number of different actors responsible for various DRM and CCA tasks (see D1.1 for more details). WP 3 in collaboration with WP 4 designed a Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection for RWL set-up (see Annex II) and a supporting Excel template for mapping stakeholders to guide the RWLs' engagement journey. These were disseminated to RWLs in February 2023 (Month 5). The guidance note included a set of questions (building on Step 1 of the Tandem Framework, and the stakeholder engagement and inclusion aspects of the IRGC framework and SHIELD model). These questions aimed to broaden the RWLs thinking on the representation in their labs, for example, considering the inclusion of a mix of government representatives across administrative levels, engaging both DRR and CCA actors with relevant expertise or access to data/models/ tools, utilizing existing multi-stakeholder forums, and connecting with impacted community groups and civil society.

This guidance was used by the RWLs helping to broaden their thinking on who to engage in their RWL beyond the partners that they currently engage with. However, the RWLs took an initial focus on bringing together government actors across levels and sectors with different responsibilities for DRM and CCA. Involvement of civil society actors was deemed too challenging for RWLs at the initial stage of the project as they needed time to first ensure the commitment of a core set of public or private sector partners, in particular the municipalities and civil protection/ emergency management agencies.

Introducing the RWLs to the Risk-Tandem Framework

The initial design of the RTF was conceptualized in January 2023 (Month 4). It was outlined in a Briefing Note (see Annex III) and PowerPoint presentation distributed to the RWL hosts to use in their initial engagements with their RWL stakeholders. A jour-fix presentation to the consortium was conducted in March 2023 (Month 6) and follow-up consultations with RWLs were conducted to explore the application of components of the RTF in their planned activities (Rhine-Erft and Capital Region of Denmark RWLs). See further details on these consultations in Milestone 12 (Annex I).

The core elements of the Risk-Tandem approach and importance of governance was embraced by the RWL hosts. For example, some RWLs felt that key challenges in their DRR and CCA context related more to gaps in coordination and communication rather than a lack of data or modelling. However, the RWLs were not familiar with some terminology used in the framework e.g., knowledge co-production, complex systems, Risk Layering, which thus warranted further capacity development (as part of WP 4) and continued support to implement the framework (WP 3). Some RWLs decided not to present the full complexity of the RTF and visualization to their stakeholders given the need to initially focus on the overarching goals of the project, and instead focused on explaining how Risk-Tandem will initially help in identifying governance and communication gaps.

Risk governance analysis support

To support the RWLs to understand the risk governance context in their RWLs, WP 3 prepared an initial set of Risk-Tandem Risk Governance Assessment Guiding Questions (see Annex V) and shared with RWLs in March 2023 (Month 6). The purpose of these guiding questions was

to support the RWLs in their engagement with current or potential RWL stakeholders, via bilateral interviews, questionnaires or help inform their multi-stakeholder workshops. These questions were designed based on the elements or questions presented in each of the sub-frameworks used to develop the RTF i.e., IRGC Risk Governance Framework, SHIELD model, Risk Layering, IAD and Tandem. These were structured into the following subsections (see full list of questions in Annex V):

- RWL set up, stakeholder analysis and objective framing
- Institutional, legal and multi-level governance and policy setting
- (Risk/ warning) communication, coordination and risk perception
- Risk knowledge and management (models, data, plans, measures, capabilities)
- Contextual critical enablers or hindering factors for DRR and CCA

Some RWLs used this guidance to design tailored questionnaires for their RWL stakeholders (Rhine-Erft RWL, Month 7 and Danube RWL, Month 13/14) or to inform interviews with stakeholders who could not join their initial workshop (Capital Region of Denmark RWL, Month 8). Additionally, some RWLs used them later in the project to design group interviews with DRR/ CCA actors to go deeper into specific aspects of governance, communication and risk management (Capital Region of Denmark, Month 21). The themes of the questions were also embedded into interactive exercises during the RWL workshops e.g., Emilia-Romagna hybrid workshop Month 12.

The guidance tools were useful but applied in a more simplistic way, which was understandable given the early stages of the project set up. The RWLs did not collect answers to all the questions outlined and some gaps remain to fully capture the risk governance landscape in each RWL. This demonstrates the need for WP 3 social science colleagues to provide more analytical and research support in order to jointly capture more deep-dive risk governance information (as planned in the Growth Phase, Task 3.2).

Knowledge co-production capacity development

The RTF was central to the development of training resources for the RWL's. Firstly, a RWL Facilitator Guidance Note regarding interactive exercises and materials for RWL stakeholder workshops, was jointly developed by WP 3 and WP 4 (annexed in D1.2). Example exercises were provided that related to:

- Problem analysis and identifying issues and priorities for managing climate and disaster risks;
- Stakeholder mapping (Who? Why? How?);
- Capacities and needs analysis for DRR/CCA governance, communication and data/models/ tools, and;
- Participant evaluation and learning.

Secondly, after each RWL workshop debriefing calls took place to reflect on their activities and identify opportunities to embed or evolve Risk-Tandem and knowledge co-production approaches in future activities and support their capacity needs (arranged jointly by WP 3/WP 4). RWL hosts were also asked to complete facilitator debriefing questionnaires in the Risk-Tandem RWL self-reflection sheet (annexed in D1.2) after each workshop which were discussed in the debriefing calls. Thirdly, Risk-Tandem was used within the first Training Module for RWLs on complex risks online (led by WP 4) including an online template/ exercise (Month 9) and an in-person World Café training exercise (DIRECTED General Assembly, Cologne, Month 12) to support RWL hosts with the knowledge co-production activities.

Guiding questions were developed for the World-Café exercise relating to understanding the problem including an exercise related to mapping the priority of hazard frequencies and management measures (in line with the Risk Layering approach) and identifying the barriers/enablers and needs in their RWL for communication, governance, data/models/tools and capacities. Additionally, at the General Assembly a Risk-Tandem co-production training workshop was conducted with RWL hosts including a serious gaming exercise 'Breaking the Silos' which provided a useful tool for unpicking the disaster/climate risk governance challenges, and the need for knowledge co-production to integrate DRM and CCA decision-

making (see more in Blog post).¹⁸ The training included interactive exercises on stakeholder (target group), knowledge mapping (see template in Annex IV), and solution co-exploration using creative and playful materials to stimulate interactive discussions.

These interactive exercises were very useful for the RWL hosts in supporting their stakeholder interactions and exploration of risk governance. For example, the Capital Region of Denmark applied the interactive exercises in the Facilitator Guidance Note, while the Emilia-Romagna RWL created a dynamic and interactive RWL workshop after being inspired by the online training and in-person World Café. The game and creative exercises stimulated new ideas for their co-production activities with their RWLs. The trainings demonstrated the importance of tailoring future support for the RWLs hosts to capture knowledge from their RWL stakeholders to apply and refine the RTF.

3.4.2 Phase 2: Growth

The Growth Phase involves the RWLs applying or expanding the application of the tools and guidance provided in the Foundation Phase to co-explore the needs in the RWLs through Risk-Tandem. The Risk-Tandem knowledge co-production process is actively applied by the RWL hosts through workshops to co-explore the challenges and priorities together with scientists, modelers and the RWL-identified stakeholders across practice and policy. Knowledge co-production training continues in response to needs from RWL as well as exploration of technical data/ models and tools to support emerging integrated/ interoperable solutions, in line with the Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2). A deeper baseline risk governance assessment is undertaken/ planned to build on the knowledge and priorities emerging from the RWL workshops, interviews, and questionnaires in the foundation phase.

Baseline (deep dive) risk governance assessment

A continuous assessment of the existing risk governance approaches throughout the RWLs is underway. The information and data gathered are compiled into governance assessment overviews for each RWL, and will be ready by the end of Month 27. These assessments are based on a variety of tools introduced through the RTF. Firstly, the assessments rely on a series of governance assessment questions (Annex V), which investigate the current risk governance status and institutional context of the RWLs. This will also aid in adding context to each RWL's governance arrangements. The assessment analyses actor networks, rules, and resources, as well as the processes concerned with how relevant risk information is collected, analyzed, and communicated, and implemented decisions. Secondly, the risk governance assessments implement the institutional assessment framework, in conjunction with a stakeholder action grid document. This step facilitates a better understanding of which roles, goals, capacities both formal and informal, and norms the respective stakeholders prioritize (see Figure 12). Data will be collected through engagement with RWLs (e.g., interviews/group discussions) and document/ policy analysis, building on the data generated through the workshops.

¹⁸See blogpost on the Breaking the Silos game application with the RWLs
<https://DIRECTEDproject.eu/blog/breaking-the-silos-towards-knowledge-co-production-in-real-world-lab/>

Throughout this phase, WP 3 provided support and guidance for RWLs to conduct risk governance analyzes, while continuously collecting data through workshops, interviews, questionnaires, and focus group discussions.¹⁹ Bilateral discussions continue between WP 3/4 and RWL hosts to reflect on progress in their RWL and discuss emerging needs.

	Actor	Position/Role	Allowable Actions	Potential Outcomes of Actions
RWL				
	Control over Action	Available Information	Risks/Benefits of Actions	Primary Goals
RWL				

Figure 12: The Stakeholder Action Grid.

Risk-Tandem Framework for RWL co-exploration

The knowledge co-production capacity development activities of WP 4 will support guiding the RWLs to build user stories to help focus the co-exploration of integrated and interoperable solutions emerging from WP 2 including hazard modelling, risk and impact assessment tools (e.g., RIM2D, CLIMADA, SaferPlaces, FutureDanube Model and DTU Cost Damage Assessment tool) as a part of WP 2’s tool for demonstrations.

These user stories are developed by WP 3 in collaboration with WP 4 and WP 5, as per Data Fabric user requirements, to aid in identifying key DRR and CCA integration challenges for each RWLs, pinpointing key user benefit solutions that emerge from the project. Their stories seek to answer questions such as: **Who is affected and involved in the decision process; What are they trying to achieve; and Why individuals make any given choice?**

¹⁹ See Annex III for the Guidance Note on Focus Group Discussion for RWLs.

practices' regarding the process to co-design integration, and interoperable risk management/ governance solutions. The lessons generated from the application of Risk-Tandem will hone recommendations for tailored governance mechanisms in each RWL. This phase may include testing co-production-based governance mechanisms, documenting emerging policy recommendations, and developing integrated visualisations of risk to support specific stakeholders' needs.

This phase is closely linked to the Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning process outlined in section 3.3 of this report. Phase three focuses specifically on Task 1.3 regarding the RTF application outcomes in RWLs and Task 3.3 which captures the learning from the application to inform the revised framework. For monitoring and evaluating knowledge co-production and the overall quality of the process in relation to outcomes, WP 4 has developed a comprehensive approach to implementing MEL of knowledge co-production (encapsulating capacity development and knowledge co-production outcomes). Although separate, these link to the overall DIRECTED reporting in two dimensions. 1) Risk-Tandem monitoring will seek to measure the outcomes and impacts to improved resilience and strengthened risk governance (overall approach), whereas knowledge co-production seeks to assess whether the co-production added benefits to otherwise technical, managerial or hierarchical processes that tend to characterize risk governance operations, and whether their perceived benefits were equally shared among all involved stakeholders.

3.4.4 Phase 4: Sustain

The fourth phase Sustain, captures the learning from the implementation of Risk-Tandem as a whole, the capacity strengthening activities for knowledge co-production, and the governance mechanism. This phase will focus on supporting institutionalisation by generating guidance on how to sustain the knowledge exchange within the RWL post-project. The original RTF will also be revised and updated based on the cumulative insights from the application in the RWLs.

The RTF application needs to be feasible with efficient use of stakeholders' resources, such that it can be continuously used and sustained throughout the RWLs. In the case of our RWLs, we have continuously engaged in discussions regarding expectations and feasibility, in efforts to better align theory with practice of risk governance. However, this affects the theoretical ambition as presented in the Framework; it cannot be applied in a homogenous manner, but instead is tailored and adapted to support the needs of local stakeholders. This will reshape the conceptualization of the RTF, and by the end of the DIRECTED project, will be compiled to provide practical and real-world guidance for advancing integrated risk management in complex risk contexts.

Through this engagement with RWLs, the framework will be further developed to support practical implementation, including guidance and activities. The ultimate aim is to provide an iterative, reflexive and process-based approach to transdisciplinary co-production in risk governance contexts, versatile enough to be used by stakeholders, practitioners and decision makers at various scales navigate complex risk governance challenges.

As part of Task 6.4 in collaboration with Task 3.3 (updated Risk-Tandem) and WP 4 Training of the Trainers models, the RTF will be repackaged in a user-friendly way to support wider application and guidance for DRR and CCA professionals through the e-Learning platform – see further details and initial plans outlined in D6.3 Knowledge Transfer Plan.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable gives a state-of-the-art review of a diverse set of risk governance and management approaches. Building on these approaches, it sets out to establish the RTF for the governance and management of disaster risks throughout the various RWLs, reports on progress made so far in the project, and shows how the newly developed framework is being applied throughout the RWLs.

RTF serves as a tool to enhance communication and cooperation across, institutions, sectors and scales of all actors involved in Disaster Risk Management and Climate Change Adaptation. The Framework sets out to facilitate data and model interoperability using interconnected models and outlines the co-design of a flexible Data Fabric for DRM/CCA decision-making, and information interoperability by supporting the flow of information between phases and actors working across DRM/CCA.

The RTF is based on a diverse set of existing frameworks, upon which it builds and further expands. Serving as a conceptual background theory that supports the ontological questions underlying institutional decision-making and governance, Risk-Tandem relies on the Institutional Analysis and Development Approach. The International Risk Governance Council's approach provides several generic tools for the identification, assessment, and governance of various disaster risks. Further, the SHIELD Model, developed and applied in the ESPRESSO Project, will support risk governance analysis through its practical insights for integrating DRR and CCA. Risk Layering supports the quantification process, as well as providing methodological approaches toward the weighing and comparing of various disaster scenarios. Finally, the RTF is also a **centrally co-productive approach**, which entails robust, bottom-up approach that emphasizes meaningful theory building exercises utilizing participation from the RWLs.

The established framework serves as a governance tool to analyse and enhance DRM and CCA throughout the RWLs, aligning with the objectives of the DIRECTED project. As we move forward with the implementation of the RTF in various RWLs, it will evolve based on practical experiences and insights, tailored to the needs of the respective stakeholders. The application process will further provide space for learning and reiterating the RTF to better assess how the approach may be applicable **beyond** the RWL cases.

Crucial steps have been taken throughout the time leading up to this deliverable to set the stage for the application of the RTF to the various RWLs (a process described in-depth in the upcoming Deliverable 3.2). The groundwork for the practical application of the RTF has been laid in the form of an applicable methodology, the integrated risk governance and co-creation toolbox, as well as the conceptual lens through which various indicators can be developed in a context sensitive manner to fit the needs of the RWLs.

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Annexes

Annex I: Milestone 12 Scoping Consultation with RWL and Mapping of Context

Annex II: Guidance Note: Focus Group Discussions for RWLs

Annex III: Risk-Tandem Framework Briefing Note

Annex IV: Target Group and Knowledge Mapping Template

Annex V: Risk-Tandem Framework / Risk Governance Assessment Interview / Discussion Questions

ANNEX I: Milestone 12 Scoping Consultation with RWL and Mapping of Context

Milestone 12

WP 3: Scoping consultation with RWL and mapping of context

Lead beneficiary – IASS | Means of Verification – Meeting Minutes | Due Date Month 13

Initial consultations with RWLs (joint WP 3 and WP 4)

Attendance: meetings organized jointly by WP 3 and WP 4 and led by partners UCC (Lydia Cumiskey), SEI (Janne Parviainen, Sukaina Bharwani) and RIFS (Pia-Johanna Schweizer) with RWL hosts.

Purpose:

- Providing a space for RWLs to become familiar with the Risk-Tandem concept through a presentation and short guidance note - see Annex III in D3.1).
- Allow for reflection on stakeholder engagement to support hosts in setting their RWL up and reflecting on their use of the guidance notes/ tools provided - see Annex II Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection for RWL set-up in D3.1 – including a set of questions aiming to help broaden the RWLs thinking on representation in their labs
- Allow for initial conversations between RWL hosts and WP 3 around the risk governance set up in each RWL and support RWLs in using the initial set of Risk-Tandem Risk Governance Assessment Guiding questions (see Annex V in D3.1) to collect knowledge locally (via workshops, questionnaire, interviews). Topics of the questions included stakeholder analysis, institutional, legal and multi-level governance and policy setting, risk/warning communication, coordination and risk perception, risk knowledge and management and critical enablers and hindering factors.
- Provide initial support and guidance by WP 4 on RWL host knowledge co-production activities with their RWL stakeholders based on the facilitation guidance note provided and developed jointly by WP 3/4

Outcomes:

- Increased knowledge of RWL hosts about the background to the Risk-Tandem Framework.
- Strengthening the supportive relationships between WP 3/4 and the RWLs to guide their tailored approaches in their labs.
- RWL mapping/ listing of stakeholders.
- Risk governance analysis questions integrated into RWL engagement activities.

17/02/23	Consultation Capital Region of Denmark
13/03/23	Consultation with Rhine-Erft
16/03/23	Jour-fix presentation and discussion with all RWLs including Emilia-Romagna and Danube

Workshop debriefing and planning sessions (joint WP 3 and WP 4)

Attendance: Meetings jointly organized by WP 3 and WP 4 and led by partners UCC (Lydia Cumiskey), SEI (Janne Parviainen) and RIFS (Pia-Johanna Schweizer / Benjamin Hofbauer) with RWL hosts.

Purpose:

- Allow for reflection on the co-production RWL workshops between WP 3/4 colleagues and RWL hosts. Topics included, the level of interactivity, level of stakeholder attendance/ participation, level of interest, and the emerging governance, communication, data/modelling needs for RWLs.
- Support discussion about RWL risk governance context (barriers/ enablers/ stakeholder mapping) that emerged from the workshop discussions (and/or questionnaires distributed to RWL participants) and factors that can support in further engaging stakeholders. These discussions referred back to answering the guiding questions on Risk Governance Assessment (Annex V in D3.1)
- Allow for follow-up discussions with RWLs as needed for preparation of their next workshops and identify any specific training needs emerging for the RWL hosts that could be facilitated through the WP 4 knowledge co-production Training of Trainers modules.

Outcomes:

- Insights into how the WP 3/4 guidance documents and knowledge-co production training were used in the RWLs
- Understanding of who is engaged in each RWL and where the gaps are.
- Identification of governance, communication and data/modelling/tools related challenges and opportunities in each RWL.

09/03/23	1 st Workshop debrief Capital Region of Denmark
30/03/23	1 st Workshop debrief during jour fix Emilia-Romagna
21/04/23	1 st Workshop debrief with Rhine-Erft
12/06/23	1 st Workshop debrief with Danube
25/08/23	Workshop follow up and support with Capital Region of Denmark
16/10/23	2 nd Workshop debrief with Emilia -Romagna

Risk-Tandem training activities with RWLs (Led by WP 4 with WP 3 support)

Attendance: Workshops organized by WP 4 (SEI, Janne Parviainen) with content and facilitation support from WP 3 (UCC, Lydia Cumiskey). The workshops were open to all consortium members to attend. Training was both online and in-person during the DIRECTED General Assembly in Cologne.

Purpose:

- Support RWLs in framing the problems/ issues in their RWLs and provide tools/ methods aligned to the Risk-Tandem Framework through knowledge-co-production Training of Trainers as part of WP 4, supported by WP 3.
- Collecting data on the risk governance context and needs from each RWL aligned to the Risk-Tandem Framework during 1) World Café exercise, and 2) Creative knowledge co-production/ co-exploration exercise.
- The World Cafe exercise included guiding questions relating to understanding the problem including an exercise on to mapping the priority of hazard frequencies and

management measures (in line with the Risk Layering approach) and identifying the barriers/ enablers and needs in their RWL for communication, governance, data/models/tools and capacities.

- The Creative knowledge co-production training included exercises on developing stakeholder target group profiles and knowledge mapping and solution co-exploration using creative and playful materials to stimulate interactive discussions.

Outcomes:

- RWL hosts being more openminded to integrating interactive or creative co-production methods/ approaches into their workshops and engagement activities to better understand the governance context.
- Deeper stakeholder analysis by RWL (using target group templates)
- Problems and needs in RWLs.

15/06/23	First Capacity Development Module (complex risks) + online exercises for all RWLs (online)
19/09/23	World Cafe exercise with each RWL – Risks/hazards, gaps/barriers/needs (in-person)
21/09/23	Creative knowledge co-production/ co-exploration exercise + materials (in-person)
21/09/23	Breaking the Silos Serious Game experience/ training (in-person)

ANNEX II: Guidance Note on Stakeholder Selection For RWL

Guidance Note: stakeholder selection for Real-World Lab (RWL) set-up

Enabling Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation requires multiple actors working together across scales, and within diverse policy domains, sectors and disciplines. Understanding and leveraging the strengths of this complexity requires collaborative and inclusive governance approaches for DRM that address multi-level challenges. Disaster risk governance includes the totality of actors, rules, conventions, processes, and mechanisms concerned with how relevant risk information is collected, analyzed and communicated and management decisions are taken. Communication, such as exchange or sharing of risk-related data, information and knowledge between and among different stakeholder groups, and engagement are considered key for risk governance.¹

Identifying the core group of stakeholders to involve in the RWL is a crucial first step towards designing governance mechanisms (WP 3) and knowledge co-production processes (WP 4) within DIRECTED. This complex task will evolve as the project continues. *To help guide this initial process WP 3 and 4 have jointly prepared a set of questions to support RWLs in engaging potential stakeholders and an accompanying Excel template to help map these stakeholders and document the process for the purposes of research.*

Guiding questions for stakeholder identification

1. Have you considered a mix of representation from different stakeholder target groups within and across the levels of **government**, regional and municipal organizations (disaster/emergency management, law-/policy-making, planning, cross-regional organizations) and first and second responders? Who would benefit from climate services / information / DRR knowledge?
2. Which organizations, departments, institutions or groups can provide **relevant expertise** (including private sector, academic partners, consulting companies, civil society organizations, NGOs, community representatives)? Is there a plan to engage them?
3. Are there existing (**multi-stakeholder**) **forums, networks or partnerships** that you can leverage? *Try to think beyond DRR/ CCA to look across intersecting sectors – agriculture, health, urban development.*
4. Are there any **leaders or champions** within government or civil society that are helping to generate knowledge and span sectoral, geographical or disciplinary boundaries?
5. Do the stakeholders have a **varied temporal focus** – from strategic planning to incident response to help capture synergies?
6. Which **groups are impacted on the ground (at community level)** and can provide representative voice(s) in the RWL, e.g. engaging civil society representatives, volunteer/community groups or local NGOs? *Try to identify avenues for engagement, for example if municipalities have a community engagement department/focal person or separate organizations, groups or networks that you can leverage.*
7. Are there certain stakeholders that you have **strong relationships** with via existing/past projects/ initiatives who can act as strong allies for the project? Are there others that you have more **challenging relationships** with that could hinder progress? *Try to involve those that you have strong relationships with, and where*

feasible open lines of communication with weaker relationships and identify ways to engage as the project evolves.

8. Are there existing **tools, data or models** that are currently in use by certain stakeholders? *Again, think beyond DRR/ CCA to look across intersecting sectors that might use integrated data – climate, agriculture, health, urban development. Try and involve these stakeholders.*

These questions form the basis of Step 1 in the Tandem framework.

Guiding questions for engagement activities

- How can you engage different stakeholders in different ways? Consider a brief **engagement plan**: who, why, when, where and how?
- How are DIRECTED objectives and activities communicated? To what extent are these tailored for different stakeholder groups?
- Have early engagement activities sought to build trust, respect and spaces for open dialogue? *First contact is the first step toward lasting relationships!*
- Consider the dissemination of information over time - are the participants kept adequately informed?
- How can your activities integrate the **core principles of participation**: accountability, transparency, accessibility, and diversity? This is particularly important in citizen focused engagement) and for ensuring contributions from non-national actors.
- Have you considered how to enable transdisciplinarity and **gender equity and balance** in your engagement activities? *Promoting, safeguarding and enabling transdisciplinarity and gender equality goes beyond providing equal participation, and requires a commitment to the inclusion of multiple voices and type of knowledge (e.g. not just scientific knowledge).*

There are a number of resources available to explain more about how to engage different types of stakeholders. These will be important for connecting with stakeholders ahead of the 1st meeting to develop the activities for the 1st meeting.

Excel template

The excel template is designed to help you list and monitor stakeholders engaged, and begin the analysis process. Each RWL has their own tab to complete with descriptions in opening tab.

- In each RWL Tab fill in the basic info about your stakeholders and identify the characteristics of these stakeholders to understand the balance of those engaged. Please note the status of your engagement i.e., if you have connected with them, invited to the workshop or decided to put 'on-hold' for future engagement.
- Start an initial analysis process think about clustering stakeholders around their power and interest in DRR/CCA (see matrix and relationships between stakeholders), try to identify the strength of your relationship with these actors (see guiding descriptions).

This is a template that can be used ahead of the workshop but can be updated as we progress through the project. By understanding the existing relationships within the RWL and working together to involve a diverse and inclusive group of stakeholders we can design more suitable workshop and capacity development activities in the RWLs.

Contacts

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ANNEX III: Risk-Tandem Framework Briefing Note

Risk-Tandem Framework Briefing note

Challenge

- To understand governance, hazards and climate change as an interconnected complex system, characterized by uncertainty and feedback mechanisms which continuously produce new risks and vulnerabilities.
- Understanding the complexities systemic interdependencies, the drivers of risk and the cascading or compounding impacts of multi-risk events to socio-ecological systems.
- Capturing synergies between Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) decision-making processes, governance mechanisms, resources and data (modelling and interoperability of information).

Expected outcomes/ impact

- Adaptive, collaborative and inclusive governance of DRR and CCA that enables resilience against climate change, extreme weather and multi-risk events.
- Co-production of knowledge fostering transformative social learning under uncertainty.

Risk-Tandem Framework

Risk-Tandem is a **risk governance framework** intended for the delivery of transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes, capacity strengthening, evaluation and learning in the DIRECTED Real-World Labs. This tailored framework is developed deductively by utilizing existing frameworks and approaches as entry points, as well as the needs from the RWLs. It combines a stakeholder centric engagement process to co-produce knowledge, alongside the assessment of barriers and enablers regarding risk governance, to address specific problems/challenges identified in RWLs. Stakeholder engagement is the central 'core' of the Risk-Tandem Framework bringing together risk governance and Tandem co-production process. *This is visualized on the left-hand side of Figure 1.*

Tandem1 refers to the **knowledge co-production process** occurring within Risk-Tandem, designed and implemented together with scientists, modelers, decision-makers, private sector representatives, practitioners and civil society organizations through workshops in the RWL. The transdisciplinary stakeholder engagement process continuously strengthens the capacity of RWL hosts and participants to understand the context, identify problems and bridge scientific models/data/tools with needs to identify solutions for enhanced resilience. *The steps of the Tandem process can be seen on the right side of Figure 1 (orange circle) but may adapt as the project evolves.*

The **risk governance assessment** will examine existing governance arrangements and contexts in each RWL with respect to the actor networks, rules (laws, regulations, formal/informal), resources (power/ influence, financing), as well as the mechanisms/processes concerned with how relevant risk information is collected, analyzed and communicated, and decisions are taken. Data will be collected through consultation/engagement with RWLs (e.g., interviews/ group discussions) and document/policy analysis. This data will supplement the data collected in the workshops via the Tandem process and help to set the focus of the

workshops and feed the outputs to support risk governance - see circle surrounding the Tandem process in Figure 1 (based on the IRGC risk governance framework).

The lessons generated from the application of the Tandem process in the RWL combined with insights from the risk governance assessment will generate recommendations for **tailored governance mechanisms** in each RWL to institutionalize (guide and sustain) the knowledge exchange post-project and facilitate co-ownership among stakeholders. For example, a place-based or practice-based partnerships/forums/networks, or dedicated 'boundary spanning' staff roles. Tandem can also be considered a governance mechanism for knowledge co-production, but the key is to embed it into the existing governance mechanisms or establish supporting mechanisms for it to be sustained.

To facilitate the institutionalization process of the activities within DIRECTED, throughout the project the Risk-Tandem Framework will identify entry points for embedding the activities and solutions generated through the Tandem process and across other Work Package activities. This can relate to improving governance through communication and coordination, model/data/information interoperability, financing and resources distribution/mobilization, and developing/sustaining capacity/skills. *These are represented in the green circle in Figure 1 and are subject to change as the project evolves.*

Risk-Tandem will involve **monitoring, evaluating and learning** around set of indicators yet to be defined but focusing on:

- *the process* e.g. participation/inclusion, knowledge diversity, continuity, accountability/legitimacy;
- *intermediary outcomes* e.g. increased social capital via networking, increased trust or joint 'products' like agreements or studies;
- *outcomes (or impact)* e.g. facilitating adaptive/social learning, interoperability of data/models/tools, institutionalized governance mechanisms, strengthening disaster resilience.

Qualitative and quantitative data will be collected from a range of methods, including workshop evaluations, storytelling/impact narratives, and documenting evidence of improved policy and practice. The insights generated through the monitoring, evaluation and learning especially for the implementation of the identified governance mechanisms and working towards institutionalizing the knowledge exchange and learning beyond the project.

Figure 1: The Risk-Tandem Framework.

Risk-Tandem Implementation

The Risk-Tandem Framework design is led by WP 3 (governance) and is implemented and evaluated in WP 1 with the RWL over the 4 years of the project. Many of the tasks (and subsequent deliverables) for Risk-Tandem happen in parallel with others, especially with the Tandem application and capacity development activities in WP 4 (knowledge co-production) and the knowledge transfer activities in WP 6 (communication).

To help position Risk-Tandem in the context of DIRECTED overall, we have identified four phases, presented in Figure 2.

- Year 1 represents the ‘Foundation phase’ where the project will build the foundation of stakeholder engagement for knowledge co-production and risk governance analysis in the RWL. The capacity development needs within the RWLs will be identified, Training-of-Trainers strategy (D1.2) developed and any subsequent modules will be developed/implemented alongside RWL hosts to strengthen their stakeholder engagement and capacity for knowledge co-production. The initial assessment of risk governance enablers/barriers will be analyzed and documented in the gaps/

ANNEX IV: Target Group and Knowledge Mapping Template

PROFILE: _____

INFO

Vulnerable group *DRR/CCA professional*

Name, employment, location, age, gender

ATTITUDES/ PERCEPTIONS

e.g. siloed thinking, proactive, worldview

CONCERNS/ PROBLEMS

e.g. relationships, finance, inclusion, rules

INTERESTS/ PREFERENCES

e.g. infrastructure, technology

DECISION/ ACTION *What DRR/ CCA decision or action is taken (or not)*

ANNEX V: Risk-Tandem Framework / Risk Governance Assessment Interview/Discussion Questions

Risk-Tandem Framework / Risk Governance Assessment Interview/ Discussion Questions

Purpose: for RWL hosts to collect information on risk governance during bilateral interviews/ meetings with support from WP 3 as required.

Output: Short overview of risk governance RWL incl. stakeholder map

Focus	Question
RWL set up / stakeholder analysis / framing [defining policy analysis objective]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which government, academic, industry/private-sector and civil society actors play a role in DRR/ CCA and/or emergency management? Who is affected by DRR/CCA related decision making? 2. What is your organizations interest/ objective/ priorities related to DRR/ CCA or emergency management and how does it interlink with others? 3. How much influence does your organization have on decision-making for DRR/ CCA/ emergency management? How do you think this can be increased? 4. What other stakeholders do you work with to achieve these objectives/ priorities? How would you describe the strength of your relationship with them? 5. To what extent do you have shared understanding of the goals/ objectives/ priorities for CCA/DRR? What is the biggest barrier to a shared understanding? 6. What is the biggest benefit you think DIRECTED can bring to support integration across DRR/CCA/emergency management?
Institutional/ legal/ policy / multi-level governance [Analyze rules in use]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [position rules] How are roles and responsibilities for different national/ regional/ local government distributed for CCA/ DRR/ emergency management? To what extent are these formally codified? (i.e. written into policy or statute) 2. What national policy/ legal frameworks exist on DRR/CCA/ emergency management? 3. Are DRR or CCA policies’ objectives and language aligned? If so, how, and what gaps remain? 4. Are legal frameworks/ national policies being implemented at the local level? If not, what are the critical barriers/ gaps? 5. What national and local level financing arrangements exist to support implementation of DRR/ CCA/ emergency management measures? Over what time-frames are resources provided? 6. How are financing needs communicated to higher-level decision makers? Are there any barriers to this? 7. Are there thematic/sectoral plans/strategies in place that include CCA/DRR objectives e.g. transport, flooding, agriculture? Are there actor-specific plans/strategies in place e.g. local authority strategy, federal level plans or national?

8. Do **cooperation arrangements** (or similar guidelines) exist for data/ information/ knowledge sharing between organizations (and/or transboundary)?
9. Has there been any **institutional reform** to support the achievement of DRR/CCA policy objectives?
10. What **regulatory/ legal/ accountability mechanisms** are currently in place? How effectively are these mechanisms enforced?
11. What **gaps** are there in the existing regulatory/ legal/ accountability mechanisms to enhance / clarify DRR/ CCA/ emergency management?

Communication/ coordination / perception

[Analyze community attributes]

1. How do DRR/ CCA/ response stakeholders currently **interact, communicate and collaborate** within the local level (horizontal) and with the national level (vertical)? E.g. inter-municipal, district-municipal, national-municipal
2. Are there any ongoing **forums/ networks/ committees** that are facilitating exchange and learning between actors? If so, between who, at what level and how successful are these mechanisms?
3. What kind of cross-cutting DRR/CCA **training and capacity development** activities do stakeholders participate in, or require, with who?
4. Do any **champions/ boundary spanning/ intermediate** actors play an enabling role for DRR/CCA? If so, at what level, with who?
5. What are the critical gaps for coordination and collaboration that need to be addressed?
6. How do government stakeholders engage/ (two-way) **communicate with citizen/public groups** and NGOs (incl. minority groups)? How successful is this engagement? Are there any important **stakeholders left out** that should be engaged in your perspective?
7. What is the **public perception and level of trust** in DRR/ CCA agencies?
8. What role do existing institutions, governance structures and the media play in defining and addressing public concerns?
9. What are the **warnings/ risk information public communication** procedures and tools?
10. Are there (or have there been) any **public outreach/ awareness raising/** education campaigns on DRR/ CCA?

Risk knowledge and management

1. How is risk knowledge currently being collected and assessed? Is the focus on **single risks or are (also) multi-risk events** considered? If so, how are they being addressed?
2. From your perspective, are the risks considered happening rather **frequently** or is the focus on infrequent/extreme events? How often the events happening on average, e.g. every year, every 10 or 100 years?
3. What kinds of **expertise and skills** are necessary to address the risks? Who has the skills/capacity for data/risk analysis? E.g. private consultants, in-house experts, universities
4. What **models and decision-support platforms/ tools** are used, and who are they targeting?
5. What is the degree of **confidence in the risk assessment**, including its comprehensiveness (inclusion of all relevant factors) and accuracy? What is the level of **robustness and validity** of data and knowledge?

Contextual factors

6. Are there any issues with regards to **uncertainty** of data and knowledge? If there are, please explain what those are and how that relates to the RWL context.
 7. How are risk management / adaptation decisions made? To what extent are **other actors involved in DRR/CCA decision-making** to capture synergies/ ensure alignment?
 8. What **sectoral plans** are (or are in the process) of being implemented that include DRR/CCA objectives? E.g flood risk, emergency management, infrastructure, catchment management, agriculture
 9. Is the management of these risks focusing on risk reduction, risk financing or something else (e.g. warning)?
 10. What **key management interventions** have been (or are the process) of being implemented? E.g. warning system, insurance, awareness raising, flood defense infrastructure, property level protection.
1. What are the **critical hindering factors** for DRR/CCA? e.g. political, social, economic, environmental
 2. What are the **critical enablers/ capacities** for DRR/CCA? E.g. skills/capacity. What capacity needs exist, and have previous capacity assessments been conducted?

Knowledge capacities

For example to help discussion:

- *local knowledge/ historic events,*
- *Technology/data/models*
- *hazard maps (with/out climate change scenarios, compound fluvial/pluvial/coastal, different return periods events)*
- *Exposure (building, land cover maps/ data) / Digital elevation maps*
- *operational procedures/ clear roles and responsibilities*
- *Learning from DRR/CCA measure implementation*
- *Citizen engagement/ volunteerism*

Knowledge needs

For example to help discussion:

- *quicker accessible warnings / impacts on schools / impact-based forecasts/ warnings*
- *evacuation routes,*
- *real-time impact data / social media*
- *social/ physical vulnerability data*
- *Information on key decision making processes*
- *Information from other actors e.g. municipalities*
- *Cost benefit of measures*

Partners

